

Social Support, Emotional Intelligence and Political Skills: A Structural Equation Model on Resilience of Jail Officers In Region Xi

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ABSTRACT

Jail officers face a very challenging working environment where their resilience always needs to be boosted and maintained. A quantitative causal research method and in generating the best fit model, the structural equation model (SEM) was used in this research. Thus, this study aimed to determine the best-fit structural model for the resilience of jail officers in Region XI, the Philippines, using social support, emotional intelligence, and political skills as the exogenous variables. 428 jail officers responded to the invitation to participate in the study. The findings revealed a significant relationship between independent and dependent variables. It is also discovered that social support and emotional intelligence influenced the resilience of jail officers by 81 percent. The best-fit model for the resilience of jail officers is grounded on social competence, personal competency, and structure style by social support highlighted by support from significant other/s and support from friends; social support is influenced by emotional intelligence grounded by self-awareness and empathy; and emotional intelligence predicted by political skills substantiated by social astuteness and apparent sincerity.

Keywords:- Public administration, social support, emotional intelligence, political skills, resilience, structural equation modeling, jail officers, Philippines.

CHAPTER 1

INTRODUCTION

A. Rationale

Academic interest to organizational resilience has become popular in recent years. Being a jail guard is one of the riskiest jobs that requires a lot of fortitude because of the institutional and occupational dangers, as well as the risks to one's mental and physical health, that await people who select this career path. As a correctional officer, they must stop prison riots, disband prison gangs, and safeguard themselves from contagious illnesses (Picincu, 2019). Lack of resilience can lead to coping with problems, bullying, being overwhelmed, and resorting to dangerous coping mechanisms which include substance addiction, consuming disorders, and volatile behaviors (Mayo Clinic, 2022). Other than that, in the article that was published in 2017 in Harvard Health Publishing stated that the lack of resilience can make an individual prone to stress.

However, the search of the techniques to a resilient life continues to be an unfinished business as recent research keep on observing, finding, and forming alternatives to attain resiliency among individuals, groups and organizations (Tocino-Smith, 2019; Cherry, 2019). On that note, Cherry (2019) has defined resilience as the capacity to handle and mend difficulties and trials in life despite all odds not to fall into despair and hopelessness and to face challenges of life whatever it takes. Sivri, Unal and Gulec (2018) elaborated resilience as capability of individual to stay fit mentally and emotionally despite complex situations and modifying obstacles and events. It must be noted that resilience is linked to vulnerability and challenges. Consequently, every person experienced down moments in life especially when confronted with obstacles, challenges and problems that requires resiliency to adjust, stay abreast and move forward (Miles, 2015). In fact, in 2001 about 450 million people were vulnerable to mental disorder (World Health Organization [WHO], 2001). Moreover, different queries which aimed to address personal resilience are pointed out to find ways in coping with difficulties in life such as disasters and calamities (Carpenter, 2013), family conflicts and problems (Bhana & Bachoo, 2011), psychological health (Ozsaban, Turan & Kaya, 2017), complex-emergencies (Karadzhov, 2015), depression and suicide (Rossetti et al, 2017) and in framing means for integral formation of individual, families, and communities (Bonanno, Romero & Klein, 2015).

For the time being, some scholars persistently search for better models and frameworks that fit to address realizations to resiliency in life. Few attributed being resilient to emotional intelligence (Armstrong, 2007; Magnano, Craparo, & Paolillo, 2016; Shadid, 2017; Alvarado, Spatariu and Woodbury, 2017; Promsri, 2019). Some connected it with social support (Wilks, 2008; Westfall, 2014; Liu et al, 2018; Nigah, Ajmal & Abid, 2019). Others linked it to political skills (Chopin, 2009; IFRC, 2016; Holmberg, Larsson & Backstrom, 2016).

Although many studies had been done to promote resiliency, but the researcher has not encountered a study that models emotional intelligence, social support, and political skills especially for jail officers in Davao Region. Hence, the researcher is convinced to conduct this study to find out literatures involving these concepts, especially in the local setting and for jail officers. Results of this endeavor will contribute to important information to help jail officers, their superiors, and their administrators, as well as the legislators in fulfilling their duties and responsibilities amid challenging custodial facilities. Other than that, this study adds to the concepts leading to modernization of jail personnel management and other related public management theories as far as the variables of this study are concerned.

B. Research Objective

The main objective of this study was to develop the best-fit structural model of the resilience of jail officers in relation to Social Support, Emotional Intelligence, and Political Skills. Additionally, the study also dealt with the following purposes:

1. To assess the level of Social Support of Jail Officers in terms of:
 - 1.1 family support;
 - 1.2 support from friends; and
 - 1.3 Support from Significant Other/s.
2. To determine the level of Emotional Intelligence of Jail Officers in terms of:
 - 2.1 self-awareness;
 - 2.2 self-management;
 - 2.3 motivation;
 - 2.4 empathy; and
 - 2.5 relationship management.
3. To determine the level of Political Skills of Persons Jail Officers in terms of:
 - 3.1 networking ability;
 - 3.2 interpersonal influence;
 - 3.3 social astuteness; and
 - 3.4 apparent sincerity.
4. To determine the level of Resilience of Jail Officers in terms of:
 - 4.1 social competence;
 - 4.2 social resource;
 - 4.3 family cohesion;
 - 4.4 personal competency; and
 - 4.5. structured style.
5. To ascertain the significant relationship between:
 - 5.1 social support and resilience;
 - 5.2 emotional intelligence and resilience; and
 - 5.3 political skills and resilience.
6. To establish the significance of the relationship between the exogenous and endogenous variables.
7. To develop the best fit structural model of the resilience of jail officers in relation to social support, emotional intelligence, and political skills.

C. Hypothesis

There are three hypotheses in this study tested at 0.05 levels of significance. These are:

- There is no significant relationship between social support and resilience, emotional intelligence and resilience, and political skills and resilience of jail officers in Region XI.
- There is no significant influence of social support, emotional intelligence, and political skills on resilience of jail officers in Region XI.
- There is no model that best fits resilience of jail officers in Region XI.

D. Review of Related Literature

This section provides discussions on the principles, concept, ideas and viewpoints from the various authors who have provided valuable inputs for the variables of the study. Resilience as latent variable focuses on perception of the self, planned future, social competence, family cohesion, social resources and structured style (Farnsworth, 2013). Exogenous variables are social support, emotional intelligence and political skills. Social support includes reinforcement from family, friends and significant others (Zimet, Dahlem, Zimet and Farley, 1988). Emotional Intelligence involves self-awareness, self-management, motivation, empathy and relationship management (Coaching Leaders, 2012). Political skills comprise networking ability, interpersonal influence, social astuteness, and apparent sincerity (Ferris et al, 2005). The last part discusses the correlation between the exogenous variables toward the endogenous variable.

E. Social Support

Bhana and Bachoo (2011) stipulated that social support is a connection such as families and friendships with the same interest, convictions, and beliefs. Though concepts of social support began long time ago, the ideas become complicated especially during the advent and existence of social media applications like Facebook, YouTube, Twitter, Instagram, and other social media platforms. Kumar, Lal, and Bhuchar (2014) particularly pointed out that social support includes close friends, family members and neighbors who can extend help when times of difficulties come.

Consequently, high social support connects to several advantages and gives welfares particularly on individuals, households, and groups in terms of bodily, emotional and societal welfare (Aday, 1994; Berkman, Glass, Brissette, & Seeman, 2000), job prospects (Granovetter, 1973; Montgomery, 1991); opportunities for monetary gains (Ben-Porath, 1980); access to data and societal welfare services (Birkel&Reppucci, 1983); and organizational deployment (Snow, Zurcher, &Ekland-Olson, 2016). On the other hand, lower social support in connected to opposites of the abovementioned advantages (Bhana and Bachoo, 2011).

Moreover, Taylor (2011) found out that social support can benefit the mental and physical health of individuals. It flows from the concept of support that one is cared and supportive. It may be caused by genetic factors and the environment lived. Wills (1991) described social support as an occurrence when a person is appreciated and cherished by others, respected, and honoured as part of a group with mutual support and responsibilities. Allen, Blascovich, & Mendes (2002) specifically indicated that social support comes from the people around like the spouse, co-employees, relatives, friends, family and even from loyal pets.

Additionally, social support helped individuals to become and stay healthy and handle difficulties in life (Thoits, 2011). It is a strong forecaster of living fit and longevity. Studies showed that social support gives much reinforcement to adults perplexed with their personalities, health risks issues and socio-economic status (Dykstra, 2015).

Other than that, Kumar, Lal, and Bhuchar (2014) stressed that social support can be connected to relationships to which one should know how to fit with. It includes help from family members, acquaintances, and importantloved ones in difficult times at the same time it can also improve quality of life like nurturance from important someone, advise from a mentor, financial support and sense of belongingness.

It was conceived that social support as knowledge, classifies three types of information in terms of their functions: info that indicates anindividual to think that he or she is loved for and cherished (i.e., emotional support), is admired and respected (i.e., confidence support), and fits to a system of interaction and reciprocal duty. It has been argued that social support's primary protective function lies in its moderating impact on life stress, rather than its main health effect. It was also stated that the concept of a support system as a lasting pattern of continuous or intermittent bonds that play an crucial role in preserving the persons' psychological and physical integrity over time and lists three types of support activities The importantloved ones help the person organize his psychological capacities and control his emotional loads; they impart his duties; and they offer him with additionalprovisions of money, equipment, utensils, talents, and intellectualdirection to enhance the management of his condition (Song, Son & Lin, 2011).

Additionally, social support includes any assistance provided by friends, family, coworkers, or other colleagues and might take the form of words or deeds. A strong moral commitment to friends, families, and institutions is created by constant and ongoing social assistance because it promotes a sense of trust. Assistance from others, primarily from family and friends and the agency, only reduced the likelihood of problems getting worse (Zavala, & Kurtz, 2016).

Although social support is not positively correlated to either crime or pro-social behavior in the supposedly predicted directions, the discernments of the source of comfort and perceptions of the conditions under which it is received are found to intercede the outcome of social support on crime and pro-social behavior; however, the moderating impacts of these perception measures are observed to diverge through sociopolitical settings (Thamas, 2015).

Social support is moderately and positively related to the satisfaction of life but not linked with BMI, physical activity, or despair. Also, social support at the standard relates to adherence to physical activity intermediation. It suggests the consideration of crafting a new social support measure that comprises subscales and is specific to physical activity and social support and evaluating social support before an intervention to recognize personalities who might have a higher risk of failure during physical activities (Baker, 2016).

Also, a study revealed that social support had significant positive associations for individual well-being. Peer emotional support moderated the undesirable effects of discrimination on personal welfare. European American peer informational support negatively impacted subjective well-being. Understanding what way culture affects the connection between social support, prosperity, and anxiety is significant for informing prevention programs that can sustain academic and psychological success (Hernandez, 2012).

Besides, it is suggested that constructive social support is associated with lower stress disorder, while unsupportive negative collaborations are related to higher stress. Furthermore, higher levels of seeking online and offline social support were linked with higher levels of stress disorder. Moreover, online, and offline behaviors were negatively correlated with perceived social support, in principle suggesting the probability that social support seeking expressions are projected to make up for the gaps in social support among individuals with higher levels of stress disorder (Pedersen, 2014).

Furthermore, a mixed-methods study, which concentrated mainly on qualitative data, discovered the lived experiences of participants about social support revealed that people who are experiencing undesirable feelings face challenges such as recognizing someone to share their emotions with and selecting the information to be shared with others. Findings also confirmed the significance of social support to people who are dealing with moods of sadness and depression to help mediate their negative feelings and recover their grief (Brickner, 2017).

Family Support. It was concluded that Hispanic officers were slightly more pleased with their jobs than officers who were White because their families were getting full support. With these variables, officers are more than happy with their work and feel no burden on their problems and disputes. Idiosyncrasies of being in direct contact with an incarcerated population in a confined space bring obstacles to maintaining a successful work-family balance, which in effect affects the well-being of officers. Initially, helping bridge the gap between the officers and their families to prevent minor problems and allow them to have enough time with their family (Armstrong, Atkin-Plunk & Wells, 2015).

Being a parent is directly related to the mutual assistance of the major and minor programs. The number of connections is linked positively to mutual emotional support. There aren't enough words to express how the jail officers were successful due to the continual and steadfast support they received. Meanwhile, ongoing motivation, financial support, and unconditional love help them carry out their mission better (Song, Son & Lin, 2011). Also, family members have received extensive instrumental assistance, such as taking care of victims, sending money, and helping to overcome personal and legal barriers (Clone & DeHart, 2014). Family is the first and most important source of support, and research shows that having a supportive family reduces depression and improves life satisfaction (Nickerson & Nagle, 2004), and decrease depression (Rueger, Malecki & Demaray, 2010).

Support from Friends. Providing support for both men and women is positively related to self-reported wellbeing. It helps when someone listens to people who want to talk about problems or stress and supports and comforts people who experience hardship. Someone's presence to rely on for support motivates them to work effectively. Social support goes deeper than its common purpose as a stress buffer and plays many roles in health and disease social organization. It may directly, or indirectly, protect health by reducing other health risks (Song, Son & Lin, 2011).

Besides, effective intervention requires an understanding of how social support occurs and the determinants of positive people and behaviors that support them. (Lakey & Cohen, 2010). Additionally, it has been discovered that officers value their friends and superior officers as essential members of their positive support networks who can provide them with emotional support, encouragement, and practical assistance like knowledge or assistance with achieving their needs. (Cobbina, 2010).

Support from Others. Romantic partners provided another significant kin relationship for prison officers on social support. Positive examples included displays of love and the ability to seek support from your friends with problems. Most of the help given to romantic partners was practical and emotional. These close companions shared parental responsibilities for helpful support, such as financial support, housing arrangements, and childcare duties (Valera, Chang, Hernández, & Cooper, 2015).

Therefore, it was hypothesized that whereas male officers handled stress more frequently than female officers by "project problem-solving," female officers handled stress more frequently than male officers by accessing social support. The findings revealed that male and female officers adopt traditional sex roles in dealing with occupational stress. Still, they did not explain any differences in how occupational stress affects them in terms of emotional fatigue, depersonalization, and personal achievement. Officers tend to seek more attention and support from their colleagues as they are always isolated from each other and never see each other (Hurst & Hurst, 2017). Besides, results suggest that providing a positive way to understand how women officers encounter and use advancement opportunities and circumstances across a range of departments, classes, and organizational cultures with the aid of their life partners (Morabito & Shelley, 2018).

F. Emotional Intelligence

The concept of emotional intelligence is new and has drawn the attention of leadership and psychology researchers. It was regarded as a type of intelligence that entails a precise understanding of one's own emotions and those of others. It assesses the mental state of the subject, demonstrating that the subject is aware of his or her own emotions and knows how to control them (Behbahani, 2011). Emotional intelligence is a multifaceted skill that is essential in the workplace (Goleman, 1998). It calls for self-awareness, self-control, drive, empathy, and social skills. Executives who possess high levels of emotional intelligence and self-awareness can project more confidence and win the respect of their subordinates.

The idea of emotional intelligence was introduced at the start of the previous century with a focus on its profound effects on human behaviors. In order to influence their followers and enhance organizational decision-making and strategic planning, executives and leaders are now thought to find emotional information to be one of the most useful terms (Al-azzam, 2015).

When Salovey and Mayer first coined the term emotional intelligence (EI) in 1990, they suggested that it was a mental process where previously independent factors like thinking, and emotions collaborated. EI, according to George (2000), is a measure of how well one can control their emotions through thought. Emotional intelligence was originally referred to as social intelligence by Salovey and Mayer in 1990. According to Stein (2009), emotional intelligence is the ability "to harmonize with the globe, interpret and communicate circumstances with others as it takes over your own life." This is consistent with having the ability to assess one's own feelings and emotions and using that knowledge to guide one's actions and thought processes (Brown, 2014).

Understanding one's emotions and those of others can be accomplished through emotional intelligence (Keating, Harper & Glew, 2013). Therefore, a relationship between feeling and thought can be used to describe emotional intelligence. The capacity to grasp one's own emotional capabilities, as experienced by the individual (Chopra & Kanji, 2010).

Self-awareness, automatic leadership, social awareness, and relationship management are four major clusters of emotional activities according to Goleman & Boyatzis (2008). The greatest way to comprehend emotional intelligence as a skill, according to Emmerling & Boyatzis (2012). They also defined emotional intelligence as a person's capacity to understand, recognize, and use their own emotional state in order to produce effective results. According to the trait-based definition of emotional intelligence, it is the awareness of one's own emotional capabilities, which includes behaviors and self-perceived emotional capacities (Petrides, Pita & Kokkinaki, 2007).

According to Goleman (1995), emotional intelligence is a more accurate predictor of job performance and management than intelligence quotient. Additional scholarly investigations and research on the topic were conducted in the years that followed as a result of the assertions (Petrides, Pita, & Kokkinaki, 2007; Antonakis & Ashkanasy et al., 2009; O'Boyle, Humphrey, Pollack, Hawver & Story, 2011). Additional studies show the importance of emotional intelligence in determining the scope, organization, and motivation of human activities (Chopra & Kanji, 2010). People with emotional intelligence excel in people-oriented jobs including hiring, sales, management, and customer service (Antonakis & Ashkanasy et al., 2009). According to recent studies, emotional intelligence is crucial for the development of human ability, teamwork, efficient government, stress management, ingenuity, and invention (Chopra & Kanji, 2010).

Workers from different generations can notice social cues and respond properly to their empathy for others' viewpoints thanks to emotional intelligence (Emmerling & Boyatzis, 2012). The combination of skills, knowledge, and talents that make up emotional intelligence are supposed to help people deal with life's challenges successfully. This is closely related to the growth of people who make decisions in challenging situations in both their personal and professional life (Sumathy, Madhavi & Felix, 2015).

Emotional intelligence is the knowledge, competence, or self-perceived ability to identify, evaluate, and control one's own emotions as well as those of others and groups. Numerous fields have successfully applied the theory, and it has garnered significant literary support (Serrat, 2017). In our theory, emotionally intelligent people (a) accurately interpret feelings, (b) use feelings to support precise beliefs, (c) recognize emotions and expressive values, and (d) control their own and other people's emotions. We begin by pondering a set of guiding ideas for emotional intelligence thinking. In light of these ideas, we slightly modify the four-branch model. Then, keeping emotional intelligence separate from the personal and cognitive intelligence, we group emotional intelligence with other relevant "large" components of intelligence. For instance, it has been hypothesized that the brain regions responsible for recognizing emotional expressions, such as joy, fear, and fury, are somewhat different from those responsible for distinguishing personality qualities, such as timidity, zeal, and aloofness (Mayer, Caruso, & Salovey, 2016).

Organizations see emotional intelligence as an essential skill since it has such a large impact on a range of business-related issues, including employee development, success, and efficiency (Goleman, Boyatzis, & McKee, 2013). Our judgments of our emotional capacity, or how capable we believe we are of comprehending, managing, and expressing emotions to react to our surroundings and sustain wellbeing, are a key component of emotional intelligence (Petrides et al., 2007).

On a scale indicating self-awareness of emotions, men outperformed women, and women outperformed men on a scale measuring their ability to use emotions to solve problems (Coonen, 2016). Emotional intelligence is exemplified by the capacity to evaluate feelings and impressions as well as the knowledge that emotions might convey. Our emotional intelligence affects how we manage our habits, deal with social challenges, and make judgments. Professional organizations should evaluate its officers' emotional intelligence in terms of performance criteria related to their jobs. Emotional intelligence includes the capacities for making decisions and controlling stress (McCall, 2018).

Professional development should intentionally include emotional intelligence because it is essential to workplace operations. Emotional intelligence concentrations in self-management and self-perception, social consciousness, and relationship management can be used to summarize the variety of interactions that occur at work. Sensitizing training to prepare employees to recognize the fundamentals of emotional intelligence and put these on in their spiritual involvements is dominant. Cognitive empathy, compassion, active listening, initiative, insight, and realistic self-evaluation are only a few examples of these traits of emotional intelligence (Makau-Olwendo, 2016).

It has been proposed that high levels of leader-member exchange are generally caused by subordinates and leaders sharing similar emotional intelligence traits. At the same time, variation typically leads to less exchange between leaders and members. It also emphasizes the value of teaching emotional intelligence to both managers and employees. Organizations must assess the emotional intelligence match between employees and supervisors in cases of subpar performance and identify individual differences. Additionally, business-relevant psychologists must evaluate the value of emotional intelligence in interpersonal relationships while making decisions (Murdoch, 2015).

Additionally, a study found that treatments for leadership training cause people to enhance their emotional intelligence. People felt that the reason the person's self-esteem grew was because they were forced to speak in front of a group and communicate with others in a way that was uncomfortable for them. The most effective training modules, according to participants' perceptions of them, were the ones that required teamwork, workshops, and unit participation (Carter, 2015). *Self-Awareness*. The ability to recognize emotions in one's own physical conditions, moods, and ideas is the first step in understanding how to perceive emotions. It advances to more complex tasks (which you can then sense), such the capacity to distinguish between true and false emotional expressions. (Mayer, Caruso, & Salovey, 2016). Moreover, it was also mentioned that self-consciousness is the recognition and understanding of one's own feelings as well as how those emotions affect others. People with emotional intelligence also use this understanding to manage their interactions with others and their behaviors. Jail staff are individuals who are paid to work in prison and carry out a variety of tasks, such as responsibilities in the institution's health and protection (officers and security staff rankings), educating them about their behavior and how it impacts their employment and coworkers (Gibson, 2017).

Police officers that possess high emotional intelligence are capable of screening their own and others' emotions, regulating specific sentiments by taming negative emotions, and enhancing positive emotions. In other words, emotional control is the process by which people create and sustain emotional states that are advised to support professional behavior (Gardner, 2015). A person was also said to possess emotional sensitivity if they could recognize the emotional speech and facial expressions of others and were aware of their own emotional condition and reaction (Schutte, Malouff, & Thorsteinsson, 2013). Therefore, self-awareness is therefore the capacity to understand one's own emotions and become aware of them as they arise. It serves as a reflection of how a person behaves when responding to others and events. Independent of one's own feelings, it enables a person to comprehend and judge the emotions of others (Muniz & Azam, 2017). *Self-Management*. It has been stated that emotional intelligence is crucial for effective police performance since officers are under a lot of pressure to manage their own emotions and those of others as part of their duty. For instance, it has been found that efficient performance of police officer tasks requires self-management. In conflict situations, when officers are typically the first to respond to incidents involving

emotionally upset people, the ability to control one's own and others' emotions is crucial for police work (Ali, Magadley & Garner, 2011).

Additionally, emotionally intelligent people should be able to manage their own emotions, including calming down when upset, coping with bad consequences, and actively removing poisonous emotions to prevent unwanted repercussions on their behavior or intellect (Whitman, 2012). Comparably, recognizing emotions is realizing how basic emotions combine to create more complex ones. Emotional control entails managing feelings both internally and externally. A person's emotional intelligence is a sign of how well they feel, understand, and manage their emotions. Managing emotions can assist people in fostering positive outcomes, preventing negative effects from overwhelming them, and coping with stress (Afolabi, Awosola, & Omole, 2010).

Likewise, emotional intelligence refers to the capacity to keep track of one's own and other people's emotions, identify various emotions and mark them appropriately, and apply this understanding to guide action and thought. The ability to harness one's emotional sensitivity to stay resilient and positively influence one's actions is known as self-management. A person can effectively control their emotional responses to situations and people through this approach (Muniz & Azam, 2017).

Motivation. According to Cherry (2022), intrinsic motivation is another essential component of emotional intelligence. Other than money, fame, or recognition, those with emotional intelligence are motivated by other things. They are motivated instead by a need to satisfy their own needs and goals. They look for highs that come from absolute commitment to a task and from internal rewards. People that like to take action are usually good at this. They set goals and look for methods to develop constantly. They also have a strong drive to succeed. They can take initiative and exhibit a strong sense of dedication.

Other than that, the ability to convey thoughts, desires, and ambitions in an aggressive, eloquent, and exciting manner is another theory concerning the connection between emotional intelligence and advanced social skills (Ali, Magadley & Garner, 2011). By assisting individuals in identifying and interpreting cues that direct self-regulatory behavior and enabling you to assist the organization in improvising as part of your mission, other emotional skills, such as emotional interpretation and comprehension, also indirectly improve the quality of emotional experience (Afolabi, Awosola & Omole 2010).

It was hypothesized that compared to their counterparts in the care industry, police officers were more considerate of oneself and others, more adaptive overall, better able to manage, and more positive about their occupations. This may be due to the wider range of policing responsibilities and potential training deficiencies that must be filled in order to adequately prepare personnel for operational activities. In order to meet the goals of an organization's employees, they could work even harder with this emotional intelligence (Bar-On, Browa, Kirkcaldy & Thome, 2010). *Empathy.* Empathy involves social communication and interpersonal relationship skills to cope with other people while also fostering positive relationships within the group. As an illustration, emotional intelligence is the ability to recognize emotion in the skeletal and facial expressions of others. The evaluation and expression of emotion are two aspects of emotional intelligence. It also refers to the capacity to differentiate between appropriate and inappropriate emotional expressions, as well as between honesty and dishonesty. Effective communication depends on having the ability to appropriately interpret another person's emotional state from non-verbal indicators. In interpersonal interactions, being able to communicate one's feelings is crucial as it fosters and strengthens emotional bonds and enhances understanding of others (Ali, Magadley & Garner, 2011).

Being conscious of other people's feelings, wants, and concerns is related to this aspect of emotional intelligence. It also requires understanding other cultures' aspirations and issues, as well as the ability to react to both overt and covert viewpoints. The capacity to interrogate and bargain with suspects or witnesses is crucial to police personnel. An officer can persuade witnesses or victims to comply by showing empathy, which can put them at ease and make them feel like their issues are acknowledged (Gardner, 2015).

Additionally, it is believed that individuals with high emotional intelligence are better at resolving conflicts because they can perceive, take into account, and evaluate emotions as well as to use emotional awareness to control their own and other emotions. This can aid in the facilitation of decisions that better serve the needs of the people involved and, in turn, produce better results (Kulkarni, Janakiram & Kumar, 2019). People who can read emotions well in others and who are conscious of their own emotions may be more productive (Ali, Magadley & Garner, 2011). Understanding one's own thoughts, feelings, and the factors that contribute to and affect other people's emotions is a significant skill (Karimi, 2014).

Relationship Management. This is a talent where emotional awareness goes farther and concentrates on understanding emotions, how they relate to one another, and how they influence and uplift others. Similar emotional intelligence observations allow managers to comprehend employees' perspectives and effectively lead them via understanding. Due to the positive traits of the employees, this results in satisfactory job performance. Additionally, it was claimed that emotional intelligence (emotion management) and crucial aspects of transformative leadership appear to be inextricably linked (Daus & Ashkanasy 2015). One of the emotional intelligence skills is the ability to recognize workplace stress and defend human service professionals against unfavorable health effects. Employees who can effectively regulate their emotions and their emotional intelligence at work are better able to deal with work-related stress, and this skill should be taught in stress management training (Bulik, 2015).

According to how a person's ongoing emotional state may foster cognitive problems. Control attitude changes to produce a variety of mental insights while prioritizing thought by focusing attention on current thoughts and eliciting emotions in response to another person's experiences. Initially, emotional awareness necessitates the capacity to mark emotions, identify their causes and effects, consider strong emotions, and assist in managing these emotions (Mayer, Caruso, & Salovey, 2016). The capability of a person to manage their emotions, become more receptive to hearing other people's viewpoints, and search for better solutions without worrying about being incorrect. It necessitates emotional control (Ali, Magadley & Garner, 2011).

A person who is emotionally intelligent may also skillfully manage other people's emotions by modifying their surroundings, body language, and interactions to steer other people's emotions in a direction that is advantageous to their circumstances or their goals (Karimi, 2014). An employee's capacity, ability, and personality trait to understand, appreciate, utilize, and successfully manage emotions can be referred to as emotional intelligence (Maul, 2012). Relationship management is the capacity to effectively communicate with others and interact with social and interpersonal problems. It makes it possible for someone to communicate clearly in trying conditions and to settle conflicts (Muniz & Azam, 2017).

G. Political Skills

Many organizations in today's world can progress their careers with the use of political talents. Organizations are essentially political, according to many thinkers and scientists (Ferris, Berkson, Kaplan, Gilmore, Buckley, & Hochwarter, 1999; Mintzberg, 1983). In addition, they argued that to move forward and navigate in such a situation, people need more than just a simple us and a will to work hard. By effectively comprehending others at work and using this knowledge to influence others, political skills are said to enhance one's personal or organizational goals (Ahearn, Ferris, Hochwarter, Douglas & Ammeter, 2004). Social effect, connecting ability, social intelligence, and seeming veracity are the four linked but distinct elements of an all-encompassing construct (Ferris, Kolodinsky, Treadway & Hochwarter, W.A. 2005).

A single person, who may be very clever but not necessarily talented, would therefore have to work through powerful networks and coalitions, analyzing people's motivations and behaviors, and influencing other people's conduct. A politician should engage in such behavior in an honest manner. The development of political abilities is a relatively recent addition to organizational psychology (Maroulis, 2015). Organizations exist in our world, and people are what give them life and help us accomplish our objectives. People consent to join a group to meet their own needs (Nourbakhsh, Sepasi & Barpa, 2016).

Over the past century, many studies have carefully examined political competencies and behaviors in companies (Jam, Khan, Zaidi, & Muzaffar, 2011). Political skills are the ability to effectively comprehend and influence others at work in a way that furthers both one's own personal goals and organizational goals (Ahearn et al, 2004). Numerous studies demonstrate that political acumen enhances employee productivity and results (Chaudhry, Rehman, Ashraf, & Jaffri, 2012). The four components of political talent are social acuity, interpersonal effect, networking potential, and obvious honesty. Social intelligence was the most important criterion in this study when assessing the effectiveness and efficiency of managers (Invacevich, Konopaske & Matteson, 2014).

Another study found that networking ability and outward honesty are strong indicators of political skill. Multiple studies have confirmed that today's survival depends heavily on one's ability to be sensitive to the needs and feelings of others. Politicians are needed in an organization to facilitate effective communication in social situations (Champoux, 2006). Whether people are aware of it or not, political skills are essential for attaining organizational goals (Braddy & Campbell, 2014). They should inevitably interact as a result of this (Robbins & Judge, 2013). Many people agree that organizations are essentially political battlefields because of competing interest groups and scarce resources. In these circumstances, using political savvy is the greatest way to grow and survive (Liu, 2007).

Every day, the officers must demonstrate their political acumen. They must cooperate with, comprehend, sway, and motivate people in order to set a clear course and purpose, coordinate and gather resources to finish the work, and promote engagement and dedication to their jobs. In conclusion, great political talents include the ability to assess people's attitudes and motivations, control others to achieve significant goals, build complex social networks, and interact with people in an open and courteous manner. These abilities enable for relationship management and optimization, which helps them function at their jobs more successfully and efficiently (Braddy & Campbell, 2014).

Political competency is the ability to effectively understand others at work and use that understanding to persuade others to act in ways that further one's own goals and the goals of an organization. It is also a systematic pattern of social skills with mental, emotional, and behavioral representations that moderately affect the relationships between predictors and results and directly affect results (Munyon, Summers, Thompson & Ferris, 2013).

Using the political skills to motivate and influence others to take action and obtain the vital resources their teams require. Contrary to popular belief, the proper application of political skills is to be viewed as trustworthy and professional in both their work teams and organizations (Smith & Campbell, 2010). Therefore, the term "political skill" refers to aptitudes displayed in situations that are pertinent to the workplace and reflect both the unpredictable nature of the scenario and its experiences. Although the difference is more consistent because of dispositions, preparation, performance, and experience can have an impact on the variation owing to conditions. As a result, interactions that encourage growth benefit people (Treadway, Perrewé, Brouer, Douglas & Lux, 2017).

An analysis of the association between an individual's years of management experience, management position, amount of education, and political competence indicated no significant relationship. Although the groups of workers had many of the same formal and informal learning experiences, qualitative data revealed that individuals with high political competence cited those involvements more frequently or in greater numbers. Furthermore, only people with strong political skills indicated formal education (Kazman, 2013).

Additionally, officials evaluate their aggregate degree of political competence as being just below the maximum, which is a very high level. The only statistically significant correlation found was between gender and political skill, with females more likely than males to regard themselves as advanced. Results also showed that a variety of variables affected participants' political skill, but that previous professional involvements, personal role models, and expert mentors had the biggest impact (Whitmarsh, 2014).

In addition, respondents received good marks for their political skills, which were evaluated for education leaders. These findings are consistent with research outlining the many roles that education leaders play, and they are backed by work standards that stress the importance of leaders' capacity to shape organizational structure and work culture (Hinkle, 2016).

Networking Ability. In order to reach a "honorable" arrangement, make contact with prominent people, and maintain relationship with them in order to avoid power and enemies, the implicated Northern Irish jail officers utilized "political skills," or deception and manipulation. They can create several networks of alliances both inside and outside the company (Dixon, 2015). Strong networkers are good at forming connections and working together with a variety of social groups. In their own businesses, they usually have links to significant stakeholders who have access to rare but essential resources. Employees with great networking skills are successful when it comes to getting things done at work efficiently and gaining essential resources for themselves and their teams (Braddy & Campbell, 2014).

One of the network's growing traps is isolationism. An exclusive network may form if employees exclusively interact with people who have their own, narrow perspectives. The leader might be limiting their exposure to novel opinions and concepts by establishing an exclusive network (Willburn & Campbell, 2013). According to network study, greater doesn't necessarily equate to better for employees. Develop specialist networks with a diverse membership as an alternative to improve their knowledge and skills. These employees are knowledgeable about when and where to install networks and when to restrict user access (Cross and Thomas, 2010). Additionally, those with great networking skills make sure they are ideally positioned to create and take advantage of chances. Additionally, those with great networking skills make sure they are positioned advantageously for creating and seizing chances (Treadway et al., 2017).

Interpersonal Influence. A person with this talent can influence others by being enthusiastic or engaged in conversation. Because they can establish rapport, win people over, and communicate effectively with people, they typically succeed in their attempts to exercise control over others. It's crucial to incorporate asking questions and listening into your interpersonal style because it's conceivable that coworkers want to be heard and understood. Warmth and curiosity have been discovered to be powerful relationship-building tools that may be applied to solve both immediate and future problems. Additionally, it has been discovered that some of their lowest-rated attributes are friendliness and affability (Braddy & Campbell, 2014).

Top-down, command-and-control communication is losing its effectiveness. It is being replaced by a more interactive, one-on-one conversational approach with the goal of fostering employee trust through individualized listening and comprehension (Groysberg & Slind 2012). Politically capable individuals have a particular style that is understated and engaging and has a big impact on others around them. Interpersonal effect is the capacity to adjust and calibrate one's conduct to various contexts in order to elicit the desired responses from others (Treadway et al., 2017).

Social Astuteness. Prison guards must maintain common sense, tolerance, and understanding. Dealing with inmates in stressful situations with compassion, empathy, and decency frequently requires being able to maintain control (Price, Kiebusch & Theis, 2017). Socially conscious workers are keen observers of other people in social contexts. They are intensely aware of their own feelings and actions and have amazing understanding of the motivations and behaviors of others. Due to their aptitude for interpreting individuals in social contexts, socially conscious professionals typically possess the knowledge of what to say and what actions to do to favorably effect their coworkers. They are also adept at making people feel good about themselves. Show them how the offered idea would assist them attain their own goals or interests when attempting to convince or influence them (Braddy & Campbell, 2014).

In addition, whether you're with a group or an individual, a variety of social cues offer perception into how people are feeling, their level of interest and participation, and their goals (Smith & Campbell, 2010). Researchers at the MIT Human Dynamics Laboratory discovered that team interactions are considerably more important to high success than what is communicated (Pentland, 2013). Politically experienced people are generally sharp observers. Their assessments of their own and other people's behavior are correct, and they have a firm grasp of social dynamics. We are well-aware of who we are and how we fit into different social environments (Treadway et al., 2017).

Apparent Sincerity. It was claimed that the most important factors that a controlling jail officer may potentially control include honest interest contact, realistic promotion chances, the best use of resources, and interpersonal skills (Price et al, 2017). Genuine workers conduct themselves in a way that is seen as sincere, open, and honest by others. I also have a sincere concern for other people. Because they are not viewed as dishonest or having ulterior motives, these personnel are more respected and in a stronger position to influence others by various tactics, such as interpersonal control. Being able to guide others expertly depends on developing trusted relationships. Since confidence develops over time and through numerous interactions, it is important to act honestly (Braddy & Campbell, 2014).

Employees can develop trust with one another in three ways, according to research from the Reina Trust Building Institute: (1) keeping your word; (2) being willing to share knowledge; and (3) having faith in other people's capacity to carry through and make decisions. When workers show this kind of faith, they will learn that it is a two-way street; the more they offer, the more help they get from others (Reina & Reina, 2016). People who have political experience come across to others as having a high level of integrity and being honest, true, and genuine. They often are trustworthy and honest. Because it focuses on the purported intentions behind the demonstrated behavior, this element of political ability is essential to the effectiveness of leverage tactics. Perceived motives or intentions may have a significant impact on how behavior is perceived and can be used to determine (Treadway et al., 2017).

Therefore, political skills are the ability to read and understand people and situations at work and then act on that understanding to influence others to achieve goals (Kapoutsis, Papalexandris, Nikolopoulos, Hochwarter, & Ferris, 2011).

H. Resilience

It is observed that several theories, studies, and research are conducted in the quest for resiliency for the past years (Luthar, 2003; Bonanno, 2004; Fergus & Zimmerman, 2005; Bonanno, Westphal, & Mancini, 2011; Cicchetti & Rogosch, 2012; Bonanno, Romero, & Klein, 2015). With this frequency of interests, there are numerous terms appearing in journals and other publications that show the growing attention for resiliency and other equivalent concepts. In fact, the attention is more emphasized on the human capacity to overcome and move forward amidst obstacles. This translates to the recognition of psychological resiliency that gives birth to another several meanings and concepts (Bonanno, et al, 2015).

Graber, Pichon, and Carabine (2015) discovered that early studies on resilience had two fields namely traumatology and developmental psychology. The former endeavored to investigate factors that helped people evade upsetting circumstances while the latter who had constructive improvement and adaptation despite negativities.

Resilience was first conceptualized in 1970s as a framework to elaborate viable ecological systems (Holling, 1973). At the same time, the idea also appeared in the works of psychology and psychiatry which was very useful in conceptualizing human development (Werner, Bierman & French, 1971; Rutter, 1979; Werner & Smith, 1977). Particularly, psychological resilience first focused on the development of children. The concepts broadened its scope to include developmental aspect of persons especially for adaptation and improvement in life. Recent developments points to psychological resiliency of individuals tracing childhood experiences that affected the adulthood actions in relationships, jobs, performance and other

aspects of life (Sampson & Laub, 1992; Vaillant & Davis, 2000; Galinski-Bakker, Hauser, Stott, Billings, & Allen, 2004).

Luthar (2006) conceptualized that resilience is a positive adjustment regardless of striking difficulties or injury. Hjemdal, Aune, Reinfjell, Stiles and Friborg (2011) and Bonfiglio, Renati, Hjemdal, and Friborg (2016) relate resilience to psychiatric disorders like anxiety, depression, obsessive-compulsive disorder, and substance abuse. Chmitorz et al (2018) recently found out that resilience is an outcome and not a trait which pointed out that individuals can cope and protect from mental illness. Hence, the study of Fritz, Fried, Goodyer, Wilkinson and Van Harmelen (2018) revealed that 50% below 18 years old have the capability to bounce back to hostile occurrences in life. The research of Aburn, Gott and Hoare (2016) include age, social status and education as factors to resilient life.

Moreover, Karadzhov (2015) established that resiliency is a heterogeneous paradigm that can be studied in relation to complicated situations such as dangers, disasters, and crises. Rossetti et al (2017) emphasized that suicidal tendencies are lower to resilient people. It supports individuals to conquer difficulties in life and to prevent negative psychological effects in the human development of persons. As cited by Ruvalcaba-Romero (2014), a resilient person cannot be intimidated by any adversaries that come to life.

In addition, individuals who developed resiliency in life speedily recuperate from stressful, distressing, and demanding circumstances (Sarrionandia, Ramos-Díaz, & Fernández-Lasarte, 2018). Sogolitappéh, Hedayat, Arjmand, & Khaledian (2018) enumerated few advantages that resiliency can do such as counteracting pain and psychological difficulties to combat anxieties and tensions.

Consequently, Friborg, Martinussen and Rosenvinge (2006) developed resilience for Adults (RSA) a psychometric scaler that tests the mental health of individuals. Windle, Bennett and Noyes (2011) agreed and hailed the questionnaire as the best resilient scaler. There are six categories of resilience: perception of oneself (self-confidence), planned future (goal-oriented), social competence (ability to adapt in social settings), structured style (individuals who are orderly and follow routines), family cohesion (measures commitment, support, optimism, mutual understanding, and appreciation among family members), and social resilience (ability to bounce back from setbacks). Since they are measurable indications of the construct, these six categories are typically regarded to constitute impacts of resilience itself (Briganti & Linskowski, 2019).

Working resilience as a successful developmental pattern characterized by demonstrated abilities in the face of occupational hardship encounters and professional advancement afterward (Caza & Milton, 2020). Resilience is a dynamic notion that can be defined in numerous ways depending on how it applies to individuals, families, organizations, communities, and civilizations. About the resilience determinants, there was agreement that the empirical investigation of this construct required a multi-level research strategy that considered genomic, epigenetic, evolving, demographic, cultural, financial, and societal factors. Given that resilience can be boosted on many different levels, efforts to promote resilience can be informed by the empirical study of resilience determinations (e.g., person, family, society, culture) (Southwick, Bonanno, Masten, Panter-Brick, & Yehuda, 2014).

The ability to successfully adapt to adversity or maintain or regain mental health after experiencing trauma is known as resilience. Considered is the interaction of the personal, biological, and systemic, as well as the environment, sources of resilience (Herrman, Steward, Granadoz, Berger, Jackson & Yuen, 2011). Resilience can be characterized as the process where a person who is exposed to risk successfully copes and, despite risk exposure, has a reasonably good outcome. Resilience thus implies a decreased susceptibility to environmental stressors leading to more beneficial effects than predicted otherwise (Askeland, Hysing, Sivertsen, & Breivik, 2019).

Besides, an exploratory confirmatory study revealed that resilience could help mediate the association between barriers to movement and being active, although there is also a direct link (Kunicki, 2017). However, even though researchers today believe resilience is significant for work accomplishment, very little investigation has been committed to how workers can improve their capabilities for resilience and how individuals could help advance the capability in others (Blasdel, 2015).

Social Competency. We observed an improvement in systemic coordination at robust police officers. While contact matters, honesty at this location was associated with a coping style of positive reassessment and strong relations with other officers (Van der Werff, Elzinga, Smit, & Van der Wee, 2017). Competence that seems especially important in the evolving world that can be implemented in various professional work projects and that which strengthens adolescent resilience and resourcefulness. This form of skill accounts for social competence. Social skills often denoted as socio-psychological skills or soft skills. A good example of this can be the ability to build a relationship and exert control or team management. Therefore, social skills can be described as complex skills that condition an individual's effectiveness in dealing with social circumstances (Matczak&Martowska, 2013).

Social skills represent both workers and organizations. On the one hand, productive client relationships, successful collaboration with partners in the work cycle, exerting control on others as well as being insusceptible improve productivity in the workplace. This helps individuals to cultivate social activity that is an opportunity to strengthen core competencies and attitudes towards employment, the value of which leads to creating tomorrow's career. Good communication, knowledge of foreign languages, transparency, and continuous growth, dedication, and willingness to work as a team improve the employees ' social skills (Bańka & Trzeciak, 2017).

Social Resource. Culture, society, family, and person are the social tools that are forces of security and vulnerability at multiple influences levels. There is strong evidence that nurturing early caregivers can improve resilience and lessen the negative impacts of supposedly harmful surroundings. Those supportive periods can occur when interventions work best (Cicchetti, 2010). Protective factors are characterized as child, family, and broader environment characteristics that minimize adversity's adverse effects on how employees cope with stress on the work environment (Vanderbilt-Adriance& Shaw, 2013). A mixture of factors allows for resilience. Several studies indicate that loving and supportive relationships within and outside the family are the key factors in resiliency. Relationships building love and confidence, providing role models, and giving support and reassurance help improve the resilience of an employee (Seen& Sundaram, 2018).

Family Cohesion. The viewpoint that some workers, due to specific internal characteristics (e.g., IQ) or favorable aspects of their environment (e.g., close relationship with the parent), could ' beat the odds' and show a positive change in the sense of adversity, led to a search for protective factors that could explain these associations (Vanderbilt-Adriance& Shaw, 2013). Family stability is one of the protective factors associated with employee involvement and maintaining interaction between a mother and her children will improve family stability and help to serve as a preventive measure against stress and problems (Cox &Furst, 2019). Resilience in working adults is likely to become increasingly important factors relating to near relatives, as this provides not only financial support but also moral support to make a better decision for oneself (Askeland et al., 2019).

Personal Competency. Resilience is influenced by a variety of factors including character qualities (honesty, extroversion, and cordiality), inner position of control, command, self-efficiency, self-respect, mental assessment (optimistic understanding of measures and unified combination of difficulty into self-description), and optimism. Such attributes increase an individual's capabilities to rely on his ability to do things on his minding all the effects of his every choice (Herrman et al, 2011). Competence perceived as a characteristic derives from the approach to individual differences. Competence is attributed to an individual's talents and abilities, as well as the overall experience and behaviours they use in a successful practice (Kowalczyk, 2014).

Resilience encompasses the learning factor, early sensitizing experiences, and features of personality, how individuals judge their situations, and the effect of defense mechanisms. Having a robust influence on how well a person takes his or her decisions (Silvester, Wyatt & Randall, 2014). Less despair and anxiety symptoms have been observed in people with stronger senses of coherence, national identity, and confidence (Aitcheson, Abu-Bader, Howell, Khalil & Elbedour, 2017).

Structured Style. Resilience is correlated with many aspects, like the willingness to make practical decisions and to take action to execute them. The desire to obey the rules to accomplish the goals despite tough times with a constructive perception of oneself and faith in one's skills and power (Seena & Sundaram, 2018). Resilience is highlighted as the tenacity, adaptableness, and conversion of complex social-ecological adaptive structures, elucidating the vibrant and advancing the nature of the concept. Resilience then further defines the trait of controlling human actions to predict and overcome risks to their life and primary objectives. It encompasses some of the critical components, with a focus on versatility, dealing with unpredictable and unplanned circumstances and reacting immediately to incidents, with exceptional coordination and resource management to participate at crucial moments (Folke, 2016).

There are three basic robust structures. These include: comprehensibility, referring to a lasting way of conceptualizing circumstances in an organized, coherent, standardized and transparent manner; manageability, referring to the perception of the availability of sufficient resources to meet demands, while meaningfulness refers to the values that individuals position one wind irrespective of their impact, and that therefore deserve effort such three are the meaning that helps organize the actions and guidelines needed to take/follow to achieve the desired goals (Getnet & Alem, 2019).

The results show that the company can adjust and communicate successfully with a higher degree of organizational structure-style, indicating that exciting incentives would arise if rules were enforced and obeyed not by workers but by the organization itself (Yu, 2018). Everyone's success within an enterprise affects how they accomplish goals through institutional models and scheduled actions (Hall, 2017).

I. Correlation between Measures Social Support and Resilience

Various kinds of social support, which included family, religious, political, financial, medical, education, science, law, risk management (assurance and first responders, etc.) are used or created during a catastrophe, as well as mass media, communications, transport, power, food, water, recreation, recreation, construction, reconstruction, property utilization and environmental legislation (Aguirre, 2006). Many networks such as religious or voluntary citizen organizations operate in response to a disaster or an emergency but are not part of formal planning and management of the disaster. Other network systems may be officially excluded but formalized and integrated into future emergency and preparedness programs and plans for disasters and for management plans. Such networks are crucial to the survival and recovery of disasters and are, or could be, a sound basis for future resilience (Bhana and Bachoo, 2011).

Moreover, the system of social support played a significant part in reducing and balancing the damages created by stressful circumstances that people face. The perception of social support is linked to an assessment of the worth of a person. A person who believes he or she is loved, appreciated, assisted, and satisfied with his or her relationships is more supportive (Ruiller & Van Der Heijden 2016).

Additionally, studies show that the level of resilience felt and shown is associated with the perception of social support (Gungormus, Okanli, Kocabeyoglu, 2015; Hamdan-Mansour, Azzeghaiby, Alzoghaybi, Al Badawi, Nassar & Shaheen, 2014; Inci, and Temel, 2016). Another crucial factor that boosts resilience is social support. People with good mental faculties typically have family and friends to lean on when things get tough (Cherry, 2019). Riopel (2019) posited that there are several strategies to increase resilience, including having a stronger network of friends and family, preserving healthy connections, improving one's self-perception, and adopting a positive outlook.

Social reinforcement is associated with longevity through interactions with relatives and peers. Stable mother involvement, social cohesion, and a healthy connection with a non-violent father, strong child-careabilities, and avoidance of parental stress or drug misuse are correlated with less behavioral issues and improved mental well-being in mistreated kids. Good friends, encouraging educators, and other individuals, as well as the extended family, will offer emotional support (Herrman et al, 2011).

Such results show that resilience has a socially supportive relationship. Facilitating resilient officers can avoid traumatic stress with the help of the social support they have and can work more with commitment and commitment. Social support is the interpersonal relationships (personal competency) that offer emotional comfort, financial aid, or assistance when necessary. Social reinforcement increases the sense of well-being of a person and increases the positive emotions towards themselves and others. Besides, such variables enhance a sense of belonging and self-worth. Community reinforcement has been shown to be correlated with endurance and life satisfaction (McCanlies et al., 2017).

Resilience is a term that encapsulates the idea of overcoming negative experiences and adapting to them. Resilience is strongly related to self-esteem, coping skills, resilience, and social support (Southwick, Bonanno, Masten, Panter-Brick & Yehuda 2014). Online learning allows people to adapt quickly to their physical and social settings and develop creative behaviour, so it is highly adaptive (Duboscq et al, 2016).

The transmission of information from one person to another depends on the social relations between them, or at least on the ability to observe each other. Acquiring social support and knowledge from a common source will then depend on the social connections and relationships between the person and the other members of their group— in other words, the group's social network (Puga-Gonzalez, Sosa, & Sueur, 2019). Results showed hope, confidence, and social support are substantially related to reduce burnout, and that resilience mediates this interaction. Such findings indicate that by growing flexibility, personal qualities will mitigate burnout in correctional officers (Klinoff, Van Hasselt, Black, Masias, & Couwels, 2018).

J. Emotional Intelligence and Resilience

To attain personal, group, and organizational goals, people must be able to regulate their emotions and motivation. Employee performance and personal development within a company are directly correlated with emotional intelligence. Resilience requires emotional intelligence; hence it is a requirement (Magnano, Craparo, & Paolillo, 2016).

According to Armstrong, Galligan, and Critchley (2011), emotional intelligence may be closely related to resilience, making emotional intelligence adaptive under stressful conditions. According to Salovey, Bedell, Detweiler, and Mayer (1999), people with higher levels of emotional intelligence are better able to handle the emotional demands of stressful situations because they can accurately recognize and understand their feelings and effectively control their mood. Therefore, it is hypothesized that emotional intelligence can reduce the effects of unfavorable events through emotional self-assurance, expression, and control.

Moreover, gaining resilience has advantages such as the capacity to rebound from failures and keep an optimistic outlook. Additionally, it can support the development of strong coping strategies and analytical thinking skills. Others who develop resilience frequently manage life far better than those who do not, and they may even be happy. In difficult situations, developing personal resources can act as a barrier to prevent psychological anguish. Positive feelings support this. Positive emotions can even counteract negative emotions' negative effects when they happen in a stressful circumstance (Riopel, 2019).

A finding revealed that there is a strong and essential connection between emotional intelligence and endurance against the officers who considered difficult employment in Iran. For individuals who encounter tension, relational maturity contributes to resilience. Therefore, emotional intelligence is an essential personal endowment that helps one to preserve inner and outer harmony and show affection irrespective of the circumstances, whether tension or acute inconsistency. Therefore, it could help to resolve tensions and peaceful societal coexistence. It has been documented those individuals with high self-reported resilience can utilize encouraging sentiments, especially to leap from adverse happenings (Khosravi&Nikmanesh, 2014).

For the police, emotional maturity is essential because their work is essential and mostly focused on human interaction. The person making the connection must have a good understanding of a successful interaction. To put it another way, it has been said that a crucial personal quality for the job of a police officer is the capacity to connect. Individuals with elevated levels of emotional intelligence are more effective at actively solving challenges, fulfilling their cognitive assignments, and communicating with others at work, and becoming resilient than people with lower rates of emotional intelligence (Ali, Magadley& Garner, 2011).

Positive organizational action offers the contextual link that makes policy officers use their talents and abilities to achieve efficient, relevant, and maintain self-assessment. It has been asserted that policy personnel that possess high emotional intelligence are more receptive to their work since they are motivated to keep their jobs (Dixon & Frolova, 2011). Psychological resilience can be described as an individual's power to put themselves together when they encounter stressful events. An individual can achieve a high degree of resilience with a high level of emotional intelligence to control one's emotions (Cam & Büyükbayram, 2010).

Resilience can be achieved by harnessing the power of individuals owned positive emotions. Positive emotions may create individual resilience capabilities of experienced incidents, was clarified. The reassessment of positive beliefs (substantial reassessment) created positive emotional experiences even if, when people are in a stressed situation, positive emotional experiences will force the psychological desire to help someone step on and carry on their lives (Rizki, 2016).

K. Political Skills and Resilience

The relation between political skills and resilience is evident. One means of promoting resilience is through significant involvement; that is, decision-making, with significance, control, and connectivity. Whilst involvement can be a means of recognizing the freedoms of people to take part in all their choices, meaningful involvement can improve the feeling of connection, belonging, and valuable involvement of person, thus affecting mental health and well-being (Oliver, Collin, Burns, & Nicholas, 2006).

Moreover, resilient people and organizations must be flexible in their assessment and response to problems to negotiate the shift efficiently. Resilience is linked to various expressions of flexibility: know how to recognize circumstances not changed, how to move between distinct ways of thinking and coping systems, how to learn from failure, and how to find significance, chance, and the potential for adverse development (Southwick, Charney, Martini & Southwick, 2017).

Building networks, convincing people, and reaching compromise all require political skills. These abilities have been demonstrated to predict manager performance levels and professional achievement; thus, political skills are positively associated with resilience ratings, especially on aspects of position involving persuasion and building relationships (Silvester, Wyatt & Randall, 2014). Political skills can be used to operationalize and calculate specific, contextually applicable outcomes of an organization's growth. The political ability has been shown to be an effective regulator of presumed entitlement actions by being immune to oneself (Holmberg, Larsson, & Bäckström, 2016).

A high degree of political ability that a person perceives correlates with a high level of optimistic resilience (Hochwarter et al., 2010). High levels of leadership ability expected substantial improvements in work efficiency and relationships with others, whereas these results were attenuated in strongly regarded politics settings. With these, it is developing stronger relationships with others (Kapoutsis et al, 2011).

L. Social Support, Emotional Intelligence, Political Skills, and Resilience

Shuo, Xuyang, Xin, Xuebin, and Jie (2022) postulated that emotional intelligence is a great sign of post graduate welfare. Mechanisms for this effect include the indirect effects of social support and psychological resilience. The findings of this research discovered the relationship mechanisms among emotional intelligence and well-being in graduate students and provide clues for research on how to develop emotional intelligence and further improve skills to build emotional resilience in graduate students.

However, Ahmad-Mughal, Nisar, Othman, and Kamil (2018) suggested that employee's emotional intelligence and political skills in the workplace are crucial in shaping employee behavior and attitudes. On the other hand, in an organization's politically polluted environment, behaviors and attitudes take a negative turn. Their research showed a positive interaction between emotional intelligence with behavior and attitudes. Furthermore, the results also revealed a negative association between organizational policy perceptions and behaviors and attitudes. Furthermore, results indicated that political skills mediate the relationship between emotional intelligence and behavior and attitudes. Similarly, political skills also mediate interactions between perceptions of organizational politics and actions and attitudes.

M. Theoretical Framework

This research is primarily anchored on Resilience theory. Resilience theory is a complex field of study that has been tackled by social workers, psychologists, sociologists, educators, and many others over the past years. Hence, resilience theory deals with the strong points that individuals and structures show that empower them to overcome difficulty (Van Breda, 2001).

Moreover, this study is based on the notion that resilience is backed social support. Riopel (2019) found out that there are numerous techniques to boost resilience which involve getting a good support system and preserving helpful connections.

Other than that, this study is also based on the findings of Trigueros, Padilla, Aguilar-Parra, Rocamora, Morales-Gázquez, and López-Liria (2020) which revealed that emotional intelligence positively predicted resilience.

In addition, this endeavor is also established on the premise of Hochwarter et al (2010) which pointed that a high degree of political ability that a person perceives correlates with a high level of optimistic resilience.

N. Conceptual Framework

Exogenous and endogenous variables are the two main types of underlying concepts used in the proposed models. Social support, emotional intelligence, and political skills are the exogenous variables in this study. Resilience, on the other hand, is the endogenous variable. Latent variables cannot be directly measured because they are not immediately observable. As a result, each latent concept has several measurements or observed variables linked with it. As a result, one of the main goals of this study is to determine the length of the regression routes from the latent variable to the observed variables.

The latent social support has three indicators namely: family support, friends support and support from significant others (Zimet, Dahlem, Zimet & Farley, 1988). In addition to being the primary and first source of support, family is also linked to higher life satisfaction (Nickerson & Nagle, 2004), and decreased despair (Rueger, Malecki & Demaray, 2010). Friends help when someone listens to people who want to talk about problems or stress and supports and comforts people who experience hardship (Song, Son & Lin, 2011). And significant others assist the displays of love and the ability to seek support from friends with problems. Romantic partners received mostly instrumental and emotional support (Valera, Chang, Hernández, & Cooper, 2015).

The latent emotional intelligence has five indicators namely: self-awareness; Self-management; Motivation; Empathy; Relationship management (Coaching Leaders, 2012). An essential component of emotional intelligence is self-awareness, which is the capacity to perceive and comprehend one's own feelings. Self-management is to regulate and manage your emotions. Motivation is all about expressing your emotions appropriately. Understanding how others are experiencing, or having empathy, is essential to having emotional intelligence. And Relationship management is being able to interact well with others (Cherry, 2020).

The latent political skills have four indicators namely: networking ability, interpersonal influence, social astuteness, and apparent sincerity (Ferris et al, 2005). Having networking ability means being able to build relationships with people. The capacity to persuade people through an effective interpersonal style is known as interpersonal influence. Social astuteness is the capacity to observe and fully comprehend people. Being open, truthful, and sincere with others is a necessary component of apparent sincerity. Leaders that have apparent sincerity feel that their word is their bond and keep their commitments (Brady, 2016).

Resilience has five indicators namely: social competence, social resource, family cohesion, personal competency, and structured style (Farnsworth, 2013). The capacity to adapt in social settings is known as social competence. A structured style is associated with routine-following, well-organized people. Social resource from friends and family is referred to as a social resource. Family cohesion gauges how closely related people are to one another and how much they value each other. Personal competency is the belief in one's abilities, judgment, and ability to make decisions. And structured style corresponds with routine-following, organized people (Briganti & Linskowski, 2019).

Fig. 1: The Conceptual Framework of the Study Showing Interrelationship between the Exogenous Variables: Social Support, Emotional Intelligence, Political Skills, and its Causal Relationship to Resilience

Legend:

- | | | |
|--|------------------------------------|--------------------------------|
| <i>FAS-Family Support</i> | <i>EMP-Empathy</i> | <i>SOC-Social competence</i> |
| <i>SFF-Support from friends</i> | <i>REM-Relationship Management</i> | <i>SOR-Social resource</i> |
| <i>SSO-Support from significant others</i> | <i>NEA-Networking ability</i> | <i>FAC-Family cohesion</i> |
| <i>SEA-Self-awareness</i> | <i>INI-Interpersonal influence</i> | <i>PEC-Personal Competence</i> |
| <i>SEM-Self-management</i> | <i>SOA-Social astuteness</i> | <i>STS-Structured style</i> |
| <i>MOT-Motivation</i> | <i>APS-Apparent sincerity</i> | |

This study introduced conceptual model as shown in Figures 1 in the previous page. Between the independent and dependent variables, the conceptual model showed potential causal linkages.

O. Significance of the Study

The results of this research may contribute to our understanding of the link between exogenous and endogenous variables and the modeling of such relationships. Hence, this research could be beneficial to public administrators whose functions and mandate are into jail management and correctional facilities. This study is of great importance to our legislators to enact laws that can uphold resiliency among jail officials and better personnel management of custodial facilities in the country.

Moreover, the data, results, and best fit model may also be used by the jail wardens in the study area to create and modify planning and management procedures for the custody of inmates that will support their resilience. The result may further guide jail officers to identify specific characteristics which could influence resilience. Generally, this research is very significant because it will encourage the respondents to reflect and do further acts that promotes individual resiliency during their duties and responsibilities. The findings of this study could also serve as a model for similar studies in various parts of the Philippines in the future.

P. Definition of Terms

The following terminologies are defined operationally for better understanding on the term employed in the research; the subsequent languages are well-defined conceptually and operationally:

Resilience. In this study, this refers to an aspect that focuses on perception of the self, planned future, social competence, family cohesion, social resources, and structured style.

Social Support. In this study, this refers to a factor that involves reinforcement from family, friends, and significant others.

Emotional Intelligence. In this study, this refers to self-awareness, self-management, motivation, empathy, and relationship with management.

Political Skills. In this study, this refers to comprise networking ability, interpersonal influence, social astuteness, and apparent sincerity.

CHAPTER 2

METHOD

This section discuss the numerous methodologies of this study, including the research design, location, population, and sample, research instruments used to test the components of interest, data collecting, and statistical tools.

A. Reseach Design

The researcher used the quantitative causal research method in this study. Structural equation modeling (SEM) was utilized to create the best fit model.

First, it employed quantitative causal research techniques to ascertain the extent and kind of cause-and-effect connections. In accordance with Dudovskiy (2022), causal investigations focus on an examination of a specific situation or problem in order to comprehend the patterns of interactions between factors. In studies using a causal research design, experiments are the major data gathering method most frequently used.

In addition, this study employed a structural equation model (SEM). This strategy, as mentioned by Lomax & Li (2013), combines route analysis with component analysis to evaluate the theoretical links between latent variables. These models can be simple or sophisticated depending on the amount of variables of any kind (observable, latent, independent, and/or dependent variables) that are included. Because factor analysis was included into structural equation modeling, the measurement conditions (i.e., reliability and validity) were better than with a single measure, allowing the researcher to use many measurements of each latent variable instead of a single one. The relationship between jail staff in Region XI's resilience, social support, emotional intelligence, and political abilities was studied using this methodology.

This study benefited from the use of SEM because each SEM analysis involves the definition of models, data collecting, model estimation, model validation, and, occasionally, model revisions. Researchers are interested in developing a substitute model that matches the facts if the hypothetical model is refuted by the statistics' goodness of fit. This strategy allows researchers to save time (Ullman, 2012).

B. Research Locale

The findings of this study are particularly relevant to the public offices of jail officers in Region XI, primarily for Region XI of the Bureau of Jail Management and Penology, as well as to the rehabilitation facilities for those deprived of liberty that are supported by local governments. The Davao Region, also known as Region XI, is made up of five provinces, one independent city, and four component cities. It is located in the southeast of Mindanao. The large mountain ranges that extend along the western border, in the northern central area, and in the northwest area leading to the peninsula in the southeast are what make the region unique. These mountain ranges are characterized by an uneven distribution of plateaus and valleys. (GOVPH, 2022). In relation to this study, there are 13 correctional facilities operated by the Bureau of Jail Management and Penology (BJMP), and each province has its own Provincial Rehabilitation Center. Despite the fact that there might be shared structures, the scope and sample constraints mean that the conclusions cannot be applied universally to other systems .

Fig. 2: Map of the Philippines and Davao Region

Presented in Figure 2 is the map of the Philippines consisting of 17 regions by which Region XI also known as Davao Region is part of. Moreover, it showed the vicinity map of the respondents.

The resilience of Jail Officers in Region XI has been challenged particularly because of the nature of the people they are serving with. They are dealing with people who are facing charges before the courts of the Philippines also known as Persons Deprived of Liberty (PDL) with different backgrounds and upbringings. More than that they also should follow the law to uphold humanitarian treatment of these people detained in their respective jail facility. Furthermore, the resilience of jail officers has been tested because of the pandemic brought by COVID-19. They need to adjust to a stricter protocols and management changes so as to prevent the spread of the virus in their workplace. Davao Region jail facilities are chosen to be the place of the study since the researcher has not discovered any studies that have been done on the variables that are intended to be studied.

C. Population and Sample

The respondents of this research were the 428 jail officers in Region XI from the employees of the main and field offices of Bureau of Jail Management and Penology (BJMP) and Local Government Units Provincial Rehabilitation Centers who are employed as regular, casual, and job order employees. The number of the actual respondents is based on Wolf, Harrington, Clark and Miller (2013) who suggested that sample size requirement for Structural Equation Model ranges from 30 to 460.

Proportionate Stratified Random Sampling was employed in selecting the sample. Since the respondents come from local and national jail facilities, a proportional number of respondents were taken. Hence, 70% of the total respondents was taken from Bureau of Jail Management and Penology (BJMP) jail facilities and 30% from the Provincial Rehabilitation Centers (PRCs). When a researcher wishes to draw attention to a particular population subset, they utilize stratified random sampling. This method is helpful in these studies since it guarantees that the important subgroup is represented in the sample (Explorable.com, 2009).

The respondents were provided with questionnaires either online or in actual face-to-face conduct of the study. Included as respondents are all employees i.e. rank-in-file up to wardens of jail officers. The respondents' participation was voluntary and each one of them executed an Informed Consent Form (ICF) or UMERC-006 to voluntarily affirm such consent. Moreover, respondents can voluntarily withdraw their participation at anytime without penalty during the conduct of the study if they choose to discontinue.

D. Research Instrument

The instrument that was used in the study is adapted-modified questionnaire from Multidimensional Scale of Perceived Social Support (Zimet, Dahlem, Zimet & Farley, 1988), The Practical EQ Emotional Intelligence Self-Assessment (Coaching Leaders Ltd., 2012), and Political Skill Inventory (Ferris, et al, 2005) for the exogenous variables, and Resiliency Scale for Adults (Farnsworth, 2013) for the latent variable, but all were modified and adapted questionnaires to suit the context of the study.

The first set of the questionnaire dealt with *social support* with indicators *family, friends* and *significant others* (Zimet, Dahlem, Zimet & Farley, 1988). The Cronbach's Alpha result is .931 which is excellent.

In evaluating the level of social support the following five orderable gradations with their respective range of means and descriptions are considered:

Range of Means	Descriptive Level	Interpretation
4.20 – 5.00	Very high	Measures of social support are always observed.
3.40 – 4.19	High	Measures of social support are often observed.
2.60 – 3.39	Moderate	Measures of social support are sometimes observed.
1.80 – 2.59	Low	Measures of social support are seldom observed.
1.00 – 1.79	Very Low	This means the items of social support is never manifested.

The second set of the questionnaire dealt with the *emotional intelligence* with indicators such as *self-awareness, self-management, motivation, empathy and relationship management*(Coaching Leaders Ltd., 2012).The Cronbach's Alpha result is .835 which is good.

The following five orderable gradations with their respective range of means and descriptions are considered.

Range of Means	Descriptive Level	Interpretation
4.20 – 5.00	Very high	This means the items of emotional intelligence are always manifested.
3.40 – 4.19	High	This means the items of emotional intelligence are oftentimes manifested.
2.60 – 3.39	Moderate	This means the items of emotional intelligence are sometimes manifested.
1.80 – 2.59	Low	This means the items of emotional intelligence are seldom manifested.
1.00 – 1.79	Very Low	This means the items of emotional intelligence are never manifested.

The third set of the questionnaire dealt with the *political skills* with indicators such as *networking ability, interpersonal influence, social astuteness and apparent sincerity*(Ferris, et al, 2005).The Cronbach's Alpha result is .834 which is good.

The following five orderable gradations with their respective range of means and descriptions are considered.

Range of Means	Descriptive Level	Interpretation
4.20 – 5.00	Very high	This means the items of political skills are always manifested.
3.40 – 4.19	High	This means the items of political skills are oftentimes manifested.
2.60 – 3.39	Moderate	This means the items of political skills are sometimes manifested.
1.80 – 2.59	Low	This means the items of political skills are seldom manifested.
1.00 – 1.79	Very Low	This means the items of political skills are never manifested.

The fourth set of the questionnaire dealt with *resilience* with indicators such as *perception of the self, planned future, social competence, family cohesion, social resources and structured style*(Farnsworth, 2013).The Cronbach's Alpha result is .807 which is good.

The following five orderable gradations with their respective range of means and descriptions are considered.

Range of Means	Descriptive Level	Interpretation
4.20 – 5.00	Very high	This means the items of resilience are always manifested.
3.40 – 4.19	High	This means the items of resilience are oftentimes manifested.
2.60 – 3.39	Moderate	This means the items of resilience are sometimes manifested.
1.80 – 2.59	Low	This means the items of resilience are seldom manifested.
1.00 – 1.79	Very Low	This means the items of resilience are never manifested.

The contents of the instruments were presented and validated by five experts in the field of research and public administration before they were adapted and conducted. The overall mean rating is 4.624 which is very high.

E. Data Collection

The researcher secured approval from the panel members and members of University of Mindanao Ethics Review Committee (UMERC). After the approval and compliance the researcher underwent steps and procedures in gathering data for the study. The researcher secured permission from the Office of the Regional Director of the Bureau of Jail Management and Penology of Region XI and Office of the Jail Wardens of Davao del Norte and Davao de Oro. Upon the approval, the letter of endorsement was sought to accommodate the researcher to administer the survey questionnaires to the respondents of the study. Moreover, the researcher made other letters to conduct the study to the respective District Wardens and Jail Wardens of the jail facilities seeking permission to conduct this study to jail officers. The conduct of the actual study took almost two months from January to February 2022.

All research materials both soft and hard copies were handled with care and respect. Every classifiable information acquired in relation to this study remained confidential. The researcher personally handed and set online via google forms the questionnaires and explained the research tool and its purposes. Furthermore, the researcher retrieved the survey questionnaires after the respondents had answered all the items and kept the hard copies in a locked cabinet and placed in a secured personal online account encrypted with passwords.

However, the researcher anticipated to encounter challenges in collecting the data. The researcher allotted ample time and opportunities to meet and explain to the respondents which incurred several days of leave of absences from work since the the respondents and the researcher are government employees and could only meet on working days and hours. Second, the research locale is a vast region and the researcher travelled from one province to the other to catch up the availability of the respondents. Third, though the researcher is employed, there are financial difficulties especially in the acquisition of research materials, transportation and miscellaneous expenses. Despite these challenges, the researcher will have to manage to pursue and conduct the study following the required research standards.

Furthermore, the researcher tallied and tabulated the data gathered from the respondents in a personal laptop computer where password and other security features are installed accessible only by the researcher or by his permission. The collected, gathered, tallied and tabulated data were subjected to statistical analyses. The statistical results are analyzed and interpreted. From the data, conclusion was drawn. After all the needed data were drawn, the hard copies of the records were shredded and disposed properly.

F. Statistical Tools

The following were the statistical tools that were employed by the researcher in the analysis and interpretation of data:

Mean. This was used to determine the level of between resilience, social support, emotional intelligence and political skills.

Pearson r. This was used to determine the interrelationship between resilience, social support, emotional intelligence and political skills.

Multiple Regression Analysis. This was used to determine the significant influence resilience, social support, emotional intelligence and political skills..

Structural Equation Modeling (SEM). This was used to explore the best fit model. Factor analysis was carried out in testing the latent variables.

Below is the standard criterion of the goodness of fit for structural models. For an index value to be valid, it must fall within the standard measure stipulated.

The goodness of Fit Standard Criterion Statistics for Structural Models

Chi-square	large value
P value	>0.05
Chi Square/Degrees of Freedom (CMIN/DF)	<5
Normative Fit Index	>0.95
Comparative of Fit Index	>0.95
Goodness of Fit Index	>0.95
Tucker-Lewis Index	>0.95
Root Mean Square Error of Approximation (RMSEA)	<0.05
P close	>0.05

G. Ethical Consideration

While conducting the study, the University of Mindanao Ethics Committee's guidelines for the study were taken into account. Basic ethical norms including voluntary involvement, privacy and confidentiality, informed permission, risks and benefits, plagiarism, fabrication, falsification, conflict of interest, secrecy, and authorship were all correctly observed by the researcher.

Voluntary Participation. The idea of voluntary participation was essential to the way this study was conducted. It indicates that there is no compulsion used to compel evaluation participants. The ability to use the current program, future services, or ties with the researchers or research organization engaged will not be materially harmed if participants choose to cancel their involvement at any time. Since participants have the freedom to leave a program of this nature at any time, none of those who chose not to continue were put under any pressure. No clarifications had to be made.

Privacy and Confidentiality. Several issues were addressed because this study used human participants to explore participants' perspectives on resilience, social support, emotional intelligence, and political abilities. Participants' confidentiality and privacy had to be protected, and any issues had to be brought up to stop future issues. Confidentiality, permission, and identity protection were among the considerations that were taken into consideration. Any personal information should be kept private and only available to the program coordinator. Confidentiality is the term used for this. Additionally, confidentiality ensures that any public reports or papers will not include such identifying information. It is vital to take into account how reports are written in peer-based programs, where enrolment is typically minimal, to ensure that there is no possibility of someone being recognized even when names are not used in the reports.

Informed Consent Process. The need for informed consent is closely tied to the idea of voluntary involvement. In essence, this means that the respondents must provide consent to participate in the study after being fully aware of the procedures and hazards involved. Additionally, it was indicated that the researcher would not put the respondents in a position where their involvement may put them at risk of physical or psychological harm.

Informed consent was primarily used so that the participant may decide for themselves whether to take part in the evaluation. If a participant needs more information at any point during the activity, it was also made clear how to get it.

Informed consent towards the respondents was acquired through the approval from the regional director, provincial officers and division chiefs. The approved letter of consent was presented to the respondents which specified that the researcher will conduct a study in their respective field offices. The letters sent to the officers were signed by the dissertation adviser. Respondents are made to sign the informed consent form which contains provisions ensuring the freedom to discontinue if they will opt not to participate the study.

Risks. Stress, discomfort, worry, a drop in self-esteem, or a breach of privacy are just a few examples of physical and/or psychological hazards or damage. It is crucial that participants be not harmed in any way throughout the actual study's conduct, whether on purpose or not.

It is impossible to foresee every ethical situation, even when there are clear ethical rules and principles. A process that guarantees that researchers will consider all pertinent ethical considerations when developing research ideas is also necessary. The University of Mindanao Professional School had a panel of individuals, the University of Mindanao Ethics and Review Committee (UMERC), who examined proposals with respect to ethical considerations and determined whether additional actions needed to be taken to ensure the safety, rights, and risks of participants as well as the study in its legal repercussions of failing to address crucial ethical issues like plagiarism, fabrication, falsification, and Conflict of Interest (COI), and Deceit.

Respondents can be possibly at risk of data leakage which can affect their relationship with their superiors. This was mitigated by allowing the respondents to make their names unknown since putting names in the questionnaire is optional. Secondly, the names and other personal information were gathered collectively and no personal informations were shown in the gathering and analyzing the data. Lastly, the hard copies of study were properly disposed and the soft copy the data was protected with passwords which can only be accessed with the permission of the researcher.

Benefits. The researcher explained to the research participants the benefits of the study to them and its implications to society, such as the importance of determining resilience which can contribute to the organization's continued growth and would also provide understanding of the constraints on growth, in order to generate data and information that every public administrator could use to develop strategies, plans, and designs that would strategically position them in the high growth sector.

This study will benefit the respondents and to the public in general as this study can acquire data which can be useful to the leadership aspect in public sector, human resource or personnel management and policy makers. The results of this study can give evidence-based data which can be used by government agencies aside from the Bureau of Jail Management and Penology and Bureau of Corrections. This research can also contribute to the few studies conducted for resiliency, social support, emotional intelligence and political skills. Researchers, educational mentors, human resource managers and jail officers can make this study one of the references for future studies and application. The respondents can also benefit this study as the result of the study can be a reliable basis in the evaluation and further application of resiliency, social support, emotional intelligence and political skills in their organization.

Plagiarism. The researcher observed proper citation, paraphrasing, and referencing on the sources and ideas coming from scholars and writers. Unless the information was general knowledge, all ideas and resources that were taken verbally or in writing from another source were duly recognized.

In the conduct of this study, there was proper citations, proper references, and incorporation of ideas on the statements presented. Furthermore, the study was subjected to Turnitin software to avoid plagiarism. The literatures preceding this study were sourced and cited. Preceding theories were used to come up results based on the objectives of the study. The study was independent from any interest and done for the purpose of contributing to the public administration. This study has the researcher as its sole author for the purpose stated in this research.

Fabrication. When a statement is presented as fact without having verified whether it is true or not, it is considered a fabrication and is a lie. Although the claim might be conceivable or plausible, it is not supported by facts. Rather, it is a fabrication or an inaccurate depiction of the truth. Fabrication in this study were not practiced. Conclusions are based on actual study.

Moreover, authenticity of information was guaranteed by the researcher despite geographic unfamiliarity, financial limitations, timeframe and use of secondary materials. The researcher took into consideration the need to respect the rights, privacy and personal affairs of the respondents.

Falsification. Falsification is the process by which study results (data) are changed or omitted to support claims, ideas, other facts, etc. One kind of falsification is manipulating the instruments, supplies, or processes used in study. Falsification also involves modifying visuals or representations in a way that "reads too much between the lines" or skews the information. Falsification was not used in this investigation. Statistics are used to support the conclusions.

Conflict of Interest (COI). A conflict of interest occurs when someone's judgment is tainted by relationships, favors, or conflicting interests, and/or when their position is abused to win favor or receive further benefits. As well as not often being immediately apparent, conflicts of interest may not always indicate misconduct. There was no trace of conflict of interest (COI) in this study. Judgment of the participants are based on fairness and truthfulness.

Deceit. Deception can take many different forms, including but not limited to intentionally misinforming participants about their status, providing false information about the researchers or the goal of the study, and withholding information regarding the genuine goal of the study. Deceitful acts in this study were not practiced. Real purpose / objectives of the study were fully explained to the participants.

Permission from Organization/Location. Formal letters were addressed to the officials of the Bureau of Jail Management and Penology Region XI and to the appropriate Provincial Rehabilitation Centers in Davao de Oro and Davao del Norte as a result of the research's formal conduct and obvious adherence to ethical standards. Only after receiving government consent was the research carried out.

Authorship. The research advisor, the panel of examiners, validators, and the University of Mindanao Ethics and Review Committee (UMERC), who reviewed proposals with regard to ethical considerations and determined whether additional actions needed to be taken to ensure the safety, rights, and risks of participants as well as of the study in its potential legal repercussions of failing to address significant ethical issues, will all be properly acknowledged for their contributions to the protocol's content. The co-author of this work is the research adviser.

CHAPTER 3

RESULTS

Presented in this chapter are findings and results on the causal model on the resilience among Jail Officers in Region XI through social support, emotional intelligence and political skills. Analyses and interpretations of data were made in the order of the objectives of the study presented earlier.

A. Level of Social Support of Jail Officers

The level of Social Support of Jail Officers is presented below and the items of the indicators of this variable are interpreted based on the scales provided.

Indicator	SD	Mean	Descriptive Level
Family Support	0.75	4.35	Very High
Support from Friends	0.71	4.02	High
Support from Significant Others	0.97	4.29	Very High
Overall	0.70	4.22	Very High

Table 1: Level of Social Support of Jail Officers

Presented in Table 1 is the level of social support of Jail Officers in Region XI with means ranges from 4.02 to 4.35 with corresponding overall mean of 4.22 or qualitatively described as high and equivalent standard deviation of 0.70. As seen from the data that the indicator with the highest mean rating of 4.35 or Very High is family support with standard deviation of 0.75. In contrast, indicator with the lowest mean rating of 4.02 is support from friends or qualitatively described as High and has a standard deviation of 0.71. On the other hand, the support from significant others indicator has 4.29 mean rating and qualitatively described as high and has an equivalent standard deviation of 0.97.

The presentation of details for each indicator is appended in tables starting with Family Support in Table 1.1 with mean ranging from 4.32 to 4.39 with an overall rating of 4.35 and standard deviation of 0.75.

Furthermore, as shown from highest to lowest, the statement *Listening to my problems* had the highest mean rating of 4.39 or very high; the statement *Supporting me in my decisions and choices* had a mean rating of 4.36 with qualitative description as very high; and *Trying to help me in my problems and Providing me the emotional help and support that I need* had the same mean rating of 4.32 or very high.

Moreover, appended in Table 1.2 is the level of Level of Social Support of Jail Officers in terms of Support from Friends. The data showed the mean ratings with ranges from 3.95 to 4.12, with overall rating of 4.02 or High with standard deviation of 0.71. The items of support from friends arranged from highest mean rating to lowest rating are as follows: 4.12 mean rating or High for *giving advice whenever I consult them*; 4.04 mean rating or High for *listening to my narratives of joys and sorrows*; 3.96 mean rating or High for *trying to help me in my problems*; and 3.95 mean rating or High for *helping me when things go wrong*.

Similarly, appended Table 1.3 presented the items under the support from significant others indicator with mean rating which ranges from 4.27 to 4.31 with overall mean rating of 4.29 or very high and standard deviation of 0.97. Arranged from highest mean ratings to lowest mean ratings, the items are as follows: 4.31 mean rating or very high for *having a special person who is a real source of comfort to me*; 4.30 mean rating or very high for *having a special person who cares about my feelings*; 4.29 mean rating or very high for *having a special person who is around when I am in need*; and 4.27 mean rating or very high for *having a special person with whom I can share my joys and sorrow*.

B. Level of Emotional Intelligence of Jail Officers

Indicator	SD	Mean	Descriptive Level
Self-awareness	0.63	4.19	High
Self-management	0.69	4.16	High
Motivation	0.63	4.45	Very High
Empathy	0.67	4.14	High
Relationship Management	0.72	3.91	High
Overall	0.59	4.17	High

Table 2: Level of Emotional Intelligence of Jail Officers

Presented in Table 2 is the level of Emotional Intelligence of Jail Officers with its corresponding indicators. As shown in the data, indicators under this variable are presented with their corresponding means and standard deviation. The emotional intelligence had mean ratings ranging from 3.91 to 4.45 and an overall mean rating of 4.17 or High with standard deviation of 0.59. As revealed from the data that the indicator with the highest mean rating of 4.45 or very high is motivation with standard deviation of 0.63; followed by self-awareness with a mean rating of 4.19 or high with a standard deviation of 0.63; self-management with a mean rating of 4.16 or high with a standard deviation of 0.69; empathy with a mean rating of 4.14 or high with a standard deviation of 0.67; and relationship management with a mean rating of 3.91 or high with a standard deviation of 0.72 .

Beginning with self-awareness as appended in Table 2.1 had mean ratings ranging from 4.05 to 4.27 with an overall mean rating of 4.19 or high and standard deviation of 0.63. The details of this indicator are as follows: 4.27 mean rating or very high for *explaining my actions*; 4.23 mean rating or very high for *understanding the feedback that others give me*; 4.22 mean rating or very high for *making sense the things that happen in my life*; 4.19 mean rating or high for *describing accurately what I am feeling*; and 4.05 mean rating or high for *encouraging to explain the actions to conflicting parties*.

In the same way, appended Table 2.2 is the self-management which had means ranging from 3.93 to 4.41 with overall rating of 4.16 or High and with a standard deviation of 0.69. The data is presented from highest to lowest which are as follows: 4.41 mean rating or very high for *feeling happy and contented*; 4.22 mean rating or high for both *staying calm, even in difficult circumstances* and *being able to control of my emotions*; 3.99 mean rating or high for *I never get carried away and do things I regret.*; and 3.93 mean rating or high for *I never get irritated by things, by other people or myself*.

Likewise, appended in Table 2.3 is the motivation with means ranging from 4.38 to 4.52 with overall mean rating of 4.45 or very high and standard deviation of 0.63. Shown from highest to lowest, 4.52 mean rating or very high for *having a career that is moving in the right direction*; 4.48 mean rating or very high for *feeling excited when I think about my goals*; 4.45 mean or very high for *being clear about my goals for the future*; 4.42 mean or very high for *acting consistently to move towards my goals*; and 4.38 mean rating or very high for *maintaining my enthusiasm even when I encounter setbacks*.

Correspondingly, appended in Table 2.4 is empathy with mean rating from 3.92 to 4.32 with an overall mean rating of 4.14 or high and standard deviation of 0.67. The data under this indicator is depicted from highest to lowest: 4.32 mean or very high for *getting along with my workmates*; 4.26 mean or very high for *communicating well with my colleagues*; 4.21 mean or very high for *being easy to work with that people choose to work with me in preference to equally talented colleagues*; 4.01 mean or high for *finding it easy to read other people's emotions*; and 3.92 mean or high for *predicting how my colleagues feel in a given situation*.

Furthermore, appended in Table 2.5 is relationship management with mean rating from 3.64 to 4.05 with an overall mean rating of 3.91 or high and standard deviation of 0.72. The data under this indicator is organized from highest to lowest: 4.05 mean or high for *achieving win-win outcomes*; 4.26 mean or very high for *communicating well with my colleagues*; 4.00 mean or high for *managing difficult people*; 3.99 mean or high for *being comfortable talking to anyone*; 3.88 mean or high for *being patient with toxic people*; and 3.64 mean or high for *feeling comfortable even when other people get emotional*.

C. Level of Political Skills of Jail Officers

Indicator	SD	Mean	Descriptive Level
Networking Ability	0.72	3.78	High
Interpersonal Influence	0.70	4.03	High
Social Astuteness	0.67	3.98	High
Apparent Sincerity	0.64	4.37	Very High
Overall	0.58	4.04	High

Table 3: Level of Political Skills of Persons Jail Officers

The level of political skills of jail officers with its corresponding indicators is presented in Table 3, and which indicators are presented from highest to lowest mean. The data showed that all indicators had an overall mean of 4.04 or high with a standard deviation of 0.58. As revealed from the data that the indicator with the highest mean rating of 4.37 or very high is apparent sincerity with standard deviation of 0.64; trailed by interpersonal influence with a mean rating of 4.03 or high with a standard deviation of 0.70; followed by social astuteness with a mean rating of 3.98 or high with a standard deviation of 0.67; and the last is networking ability with a mean rating of 3.78 or high with a standard deviation of 0.72.

The data appended in Table 3.1 showed the networking ability showed an overall mean rating of 3.78 or High with a 0.72 standard deviation. Under this indicator, 3.84 mean rating or high for *having developed a large network of colleagues and associates at work who I can call on for support when I really need to get things done*. Trailed by 3.79 mean ratings for both *spending a lot of time and effort at work networking with others* and *spending a lot of time at work developing connections with others*. Followed by 3.77 mean rating or high for *being good at building relationships with influential people at work*. Then, by 3.75 mean rating or high for *knowing and am well connected to a lot of important people*. And 3.72 mean rating or high for *being good at using my connections and network to make things happen at work*.

Furthermore, Table 3.2 presented the indicator Interpersonal Influence has an overall mean rating of 4.03 or high with standard deviation of 0.70 and with the following details presented from highest to lowest: 4.12 mean rating or high for *being able to make most people feel comfortable and at ease around me*; 4.09 mean rating or high for *being able to communicate easily and effectively with others*; 4.05 mean rating or high for *it is easy for me to develop good rapport with most people*; and 3.84 mean rating or high for *being good at getting people to like me*.

Consequently, Table 3.3 showed the social astuteness indicator with a 3.98 overall mean rating or high with a 0.67 standard deviation. This includes 4.04 mean rating or high for *paying close attention to people's facial expressions*; 4.01 mean rating or high for *I seem to instinctively know the right things to say or do to influence others*; 3.99 mean rating or high for *understanding people very well*; 3.98 mean rating or high for *having intuition about how to present myself to others*; and 3.88 mean rating or high for *being particularly good at sensing the motivations and hidden agendas of others*.

Moreover, apparent sincerity indicator in Table 3.4 showed 4.37 overall mean or very high and with a 0.64 standard deviation. Under this indicator, 4.45 mean rating or very high for *being sincere in what I say and do*; 4.39 mean rating or very high for *trying to be genuine in what I say and do when communicating with others*; and 4.27 mean rating or very high for *showing a genuine interest in other people*.

D. Level of Resilience of Jail Officers

The level of resilience of jail officers is presented and interpreted based on the result with the following indicators: social competence, social resource, family cohesion, personal competence, and structure style.

Reflected in Table 4 that the resilience of jail officers had means range from 4.01 to 4.45 with an overall mean rating of 4.26 or a qualitatively described as very high and a standard deviation of 0.55. As presented from the data that the indicator with the highest mean rating of 4.45 or very high is family cohesion with standard deviation of 0.68; followed by personal competence with a mean rating of 4.42 or very high with a standard deviation of 0.63; trailed by social resource with a mean rating of 4.32 or very high with a standard deviation of 0.66; tailed by structured style with a mean rating of 4.09 or high with a standard deviation of 0.58; and social competence with a mean rating of 4.01 or high with a standard deviation of 0.64.

Indicator	SD	Mean	Descriptive Level
Social Competence	0.64	4.01	High
Social Resource	0.66	4.32	Very High
Family Cohesion	0.68	4.45	Very High
Personal Competence	0.63	4.42	Very High
Structured Style	0.58	4.09	High
Overall	0.55	4.26	Very High

Table 4: Level of Resilience of Jail Officers

It could be gleaned from the appended Table 4.1 that the indicator social competence had an overall mean rating of 4.01 or High and with a 0.64 standard deviation. This included a mean rating of 4.28 or very high for *being flexible in social situations*; 4.10 mean rating or high for *establishing friendly relations with others easily*; 4.09 mean rating or high for *communicating well with new people*; 3.94 mean rating or high for *enjoying being with other people*; 3.85 mean rating or high for *finding topics to talk about with others easily*; and 3.80 mean rating or high for *laughing easily*.

Moreover, Table 4.2 showed the social resource indicator had an overall mean of 4.32 or very high and a standard deviation of 0.66. This included the following items: 4.46 mean rating or very high for *having family members and friends who encourage me*; 4.45 mean rating or very high for *having family members and friends who appreciate my abilities*; 4.42 mean rating or very high for *having family members and friends who help me*; 4.41 mean rating or very high for *having someone who helps me when needed*; 4.25 mean rating or very high for *being quickly informed when a family member has a problem*; 4.20 mean rating or very high for *having strong connections among my friends*; and 4.04 mean rating or high for *discussing personal issues with friends and/or family members*.

Subsequently, Table 4.3 showed that 4.45 overall mean rating or very high with a 0.68 standard deviation summarized the family cohesion indicator. This included 4.64 mean rating or very high for *enjoying being with family*; 4.49 mean rating or very high for *having strong connections in my family*; 4.47 mean rating or very high for *enjoying doing common activity with my family*; 4.39 mean ratings or very high for *being optimistic in difficult situations*; 4.38 mean rating or very high for *having a family who agrees on important affairs in life*; and 4.33 mean rating or very high for *being honest to my family as they are to me*.

Furthermore, Table 4.4 presented the indicator personal competence with an overall mean of 4.42 or very high with a standard deviation of 0.63. The mean scores of the items under this indicator are as follows: 4.58 mean rating or very high for *knowing there is a better future after difficult situations*; 4.49 mean rating or very high for *having realistic plans for the future*; 4.48 mean rating or very high for *having a good future that awaits me*; 4.47 mean rating or very high for *knowing I will succeed in my endeavors*; 4.42 mean ratings or very high for both *believing in my abilities* and *solving my personal problems*; 4.37 mean rating or very high for *knowing how to get to my aims*; 4.35 mean rating or very high for *trusting my judgments and decisions*; 4.32 mean rating or very high for *finding a way to solve problems regardless of what happens*; and 4.27 mean rating or very high for *achieving goals I set*.

Further, Table 4.5 showed the structured style indicator had an overall mean of 4.09 or high and a standard deviation of 0.58. This included the following items: 4.43 mean rating or very high for *having a goal, I do my best to attain it*; 4.33 mean rating or very high for *preferring to have plans for my activities*; 4.04 mean rating or high for *maintaining daily rules even in difficult situations*; and 3.55 mean rating or high for *following regular rules to make my daily life easier*.

E. Significance on the Relationship Between Social Support and Resilience of Jail Officers in Region XI

Shown in Table 5 is the relationship between social support and resilience of jail officers with overall r-value of .819 and p-value of .000 very much lower than .05 level of significance set in this study. It is therefore stated that social support provides significant bearing on the resilience of jail officers. The finding signifies that the increase of social support increases the resilience of jail officers.

Presenting the details of the data, family support is correlated to: social competence with r-value of .451 and p-value of .000 (*Significant*); social resource.

Social Support	Resilience					Overall
	Social Competence	Social Resource	Family Cohesion	Personal Competence	Structured Style	
Family Support	.451**	.783**	.820**	.656**	.617**	.779**
Support from Friends	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000
Support from Significant Others	.612**	.781**	.661**	.605**	.577**	.756**
Overall	.459**	.630**	.514**	.519**	.485**	.608**
	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000
	.584**	.839**	.758**	.682**	.643**	.819**
	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000

Table 5: Significance on the Relationship between Social Support and Resilience of Jail Officers

with r-value of .783 and p-value of .000 (*Significant*); family cohesion with r-value of .820 and p-value of .000 (*Significant*); personal competence with r-value of .656 and p-value of .000 (*Significant*); and structured style with r-value of .617 and p-value of .000 (*Significant*). The overall results on the correlation between family support and resilience of jail officers gained an r-value of .779 and p-value of .000 (*Significant*).

Likewise, support from friends is correlated to: social competence with r-value of .612 and p-value of .000 (*Significant*); social resource with r-value of .781 and p-value of .000 (*Significant*); family cohesion with r-value of .661 and p-value of .000 (*Significant*); personal competence with r-value of .605 and p-value of .000 (*Significant*); and structured style with r-value of .577 and p-value of .000 (*Significant*). The overall results on the correlation between support from friends and resilience of jail officers gained an r-value of .756 and p-value of .000 (*Significant*).

Moreover, support from significant others is correlated to: social competence with r-value of .459 and p-value of .000 (*Significant*); social resource with r-value of .630 and p-value of .000 (*Significant*); family cohesion with r-value of .514 and p-value of .000 (*Significant*); personal competence with r-value of .519 and p-value of .000 (*Significant*); and structured style with r-value of .485 and p-value of .000 (*Significant*). The overall results on the correlation between support from friends and resilience of jail officers gained an r-value of .608 and p-value of .000 (*Significant*).

F. Significance on the Relationship Between Emotional Intelligence and Resilience of Jail Officers in Region XI

Emotional Intelligence	Resilience					Overall
	Social Competence	Social Resource	Family Cohesion	Personal Competence	Structured Style	
Self-awareness	.610** .000	.658** .000	.645** .000	.749** .000	.719** .000	.785** .000
Self-management	.570** .000	.590** .000	.593** .000	.749** .000	.752** .000	.753** .000
Motivation	.551** .000	.663** .000	.648** .000	.825** .000	.787** .000	.805** .000
Empathy	.636** .000	.639** .000	.592** .000	.720** .000	.692** .000	.762** .000
Relationship Management	.637** .000	.563** .000	.482** .000	.607** .000	.630** .000	.676** .000
Overall	.682** .000	.704** .000	.668** .000	.825** .000	.810** .000	.855** .000

Table 6: Significance on the Relationship between Emotional Intelligence and Resilience of Jail Officers

Shown in Table 6 is the relationship between emotional intelligence and resilience of jail officers with overall r-value of .855 and p-value of .000 which is lower than .05 level of significance. It is therefore implied that emotional intelligence provides significant direction on the resilience of jail officers. The finding signifies that the boost of social support raises the resilience of jail officers.

Data show that self-awareness is correlated to: social competence with r-value of .610 and p-value of .000 (*Significant*); social resource with r-value of .658 and p-value of .000 (*Significant*); family cohesion with r-value of .645 and p-value of .000 (*Significant*); personal competence with r-value of .749 and p-value of .000 (*Significant*); and structured style with r-value of .719 and p-value of .000 (*Significant*). The overall results on the correlation between self-awareness and resilience of jail officers gained an r-value of .785 and p-value of .000 (*Significant*).

Other than that, self-management is correlated to: social competence with r-value of .570 and p-value of .000 (*Significant*); social resource with r-value of .590 and p-value of .000 (*Significant*); family cohesion with r-value of .593 and p-value of .000 (*Significant*); personal competence with r-value of .749 and p-value of .000 (*Significant*); and structured style with r-value of .752 and p-value of .000 (*Significant*). The overall results on the correlation between self-management and resilience of jail officers gained an r-value of .753 and p-value of .000 (*Significant*).

Moreover, motivation is correlated to: social competence with r-value of .551 and p-value of .000 (*Significant*); social resource with r-value of .663 and p-value of .000 (*Significant*); family cohesion with r-value of .648 and p-value of .000 (*Significant*); personal competence with r-value of .825 and p-value of .000 (*Significant*); and structured style with r-value of .787 and p-value of .000 (*Significant*). The overall results on the correlation between motivation and resilience of jail officers gained an r-value of .805 and p-value of .000 (*Significant*).

Additionally, empathy is correlated to: social competence with r-value of .636 and p-value of .000 (*Significant*); social resource with r-value of .639 and p-value of .000 (*Significant*); family cohesion with r-value of .592 and p-value of .000 (*Significant*); personal competence with r-value of .720 and p-value of .000 (*Significant*); and structured style with r-value of .692 and p-value of .000 (*Significant*). The overall results on the correlation between empathy and resilience of jail officers obtained an r-value of .762 and p-value of .000 (*Significant*).

Furthermore, relationship management is correlated to: social competence with r-value of .637 and p-value of .000 (*Significant*); social resource with r-value of .563 and p-value of .000 (*Significant*); family cohesion with r-value of .482 and p-value of .000 (*Significant*); personal competence with r-value of .607 and p-value of .000 (*Significant*); and structured style with r-value of .630 and p-value of .000 (*Significant*). The overall results on the correlation between support from friends and resilience of jail officers gained an r-value of .676 and p-value of .000 (*Significant*).

G. Significance on the Relationship Between Political Skills and Resilience of Jail Officers in Region XI

Presented in Table 7 is the relationship between political skills and resilience of jail officers with overall r-value of .764 and p-value of .000 (*Significant*). It is therefore inferred that political skills support significantly on the resilience of jail officers. The finding signifies that the rise of political skills boosts the resilience of jail officers.

Political Skills	Resilience					Overall
	Social Competence	Social Resource	Family Cohesion	Personal Competence	Structured Style	
Networking Ability	.557** .000	.431** .000	.363** .000	.457** .000	.472** .000	.529** .000
Interpersonal Influence	.681** .000	.598** .000	.518** .000	.616** .000	.598** .000	.699** .000
Social Astuteness	.589** .000	.504** .000	.523** .000	.609** .000	.628** .000	.662** .000
Apparent Sincerity	.599** .000	.596** .000	.635** .000	.693** .000	.668** .000	.741** .000
Overall	.707** .000	.618** .000	.590** .000	.689** .000	.686** .000	.764** .000

Table 7: Significance on the Relationship between Political Skills and Resilience of Jail Officers

As revealed, networking ability is correlated to: social competence with r-value of .557 and p-value of .000 (*Significant*); social resource with r-value of .431 and p-value of .000 (*Significant*); family cohesion with r-value of .363 and p-value of .000 (*Significant*); personal competence with r-value of .457 and p-value of .000 (*Significant*); and structured style with r-value of .472 and p-value of .000 (*Significant*). The overall results on the correlation between networking ability and resilience of jail officers gained an r-value of .529 and p-value of .000 (*Significant*).

Moreover, interpersonal influence is correlated to: social competence with r-value of .681 and p-value of .000 (*Significant*); social resource with r-value of .598 and p-value of .000 (*Significant*); family cohesion with r-value of .518 and p-value of .000 (*Significant*); personal competence with r-value of .616 and p-value of .000 (*Significant*); and structured style with r-value of .598 and p-value of .000 (*Significant*). The overall results on the correlation between interpersonal influence and resilience of jail officers gained an r-value of .699 and p-value of .000 (*Significant*).

Besides, social astuteness is correlated to: social competence with r-value of .589 and p-value of .000 (*Significant*); social resource with r-value of .504 and p-value of .000 (*Significant*); family cohesion with r-value of .523 and p-value of .000 (*Significant*); personal competence with r-value of .609 and p-value of .000 (*Significant*); and structured style with r-value of .628 and p-value of .000 (*Significant*). The overall results on the correlation between social astuteness and resilience of jail officers gained an r-value of .662 and p-value of .000 (*Significant*).

In addition, apparent sincerity is correlated to: social competence with r-value of .559 and p-value of .000 (*Significant*); social resource with r-value of .596 and p-value of .000 (*Significant*); family cohesion with r-value of .635 and p-value of .000 (*Significant*); personal competence with r-value of .693 and p-value of .000 (*Significant*); and structured style with r-value of .668 and p-value of .000 (*Significant*). The overall results on the correlation between apparent sincerity and resilience of jail officers obtained an r-value of .741 and p-value of .000 (*Significant*).

H. Significance on the Combined Influence of Social Support, Emotional Intelligence, and Political Skills on the Resilience of Jail Officers

Resilience				
Exogenous Variables	<i>B</i>	β	<i>t</i>	<i>Sig.</i>
Constant	.732		8.621	.000
<i>Social Support</i>	.326	.415	13.301	.000
<i>Emotional Intelligence</i>	.497	.536	12.461	.000
<i>Political Skills</i>	.019	.020	.497	.620
R	.902			
R ²	.814			
ΔR	.813			
F	618.310			
ρ	.000			

Table 8: Significance on the Influence of Social Support, Emotional Intelligence and Political Skills on the Resilience of Jail Officers

Presented in Table 8 is the significance on the influence of social support, emotional intelligence, and political skills on the resilience of jail officers with a computed F-value of 618.310, R-value of .902, adjusted R2 value of .814 and p-value of .000 which is lower than .05 level of significance set in this study and concurred the rejection of the null hypothesis in favor to the alternative hypothesis. This result showed that social support, emotional intelligence, and political skills influence resilience of jail officers.

It could be gleaned from the data that social support had standardized and unstandardized coefficients of .326 and .415, t-value of 13.301 and p-value of .000 (*Significant*); emotional intelligence had standardized and unstandardized coefficients of .497 and .536, t-value of 12.461 and p-value of .000 (*Significant*); and political skills showed standardized and unstandardized coefficients of .019 and .020, t-value of .497 and p-value of .620 (*non-significant*).

Moreover, the regression model showed that the combined influence of the three factors on the resilience is at 81.40 percent, which is significant at $p < 0.001$. The model implies that social support, emotional intelligence, and political skills can explain 81.40% of the resilience of jail officers. In contrast, the other 18.60% may be attributed to other factors not covered in this study.

I. Model Development

Several models were generated to determine the causal relationship of social support, emotional intelligence, and political skills to the jail officers of Region XI. Hence, modification for the first generated model as shown in Figure 1 is imperative to meet the requirements of the goodness of fit measures.

J. Generated Model 5

Shown in Figure 7 is the generated structural model 5 which represents the standardize solution for the study. Results indicated that the latent variable political skills with social astuteness and apparent sincerity measured indicators have significant relationship to emotional intelligence; indicators networking ability and interpersonal influence have no significant correlation. Also, revealed in the model is emotional intelligence represented by self-awareness and empathy indicators showing significant relationship to social support. This is contrary to self-management, motivation, and relationship management indicators which showed no significance.

Fig. 3: Best Fit Model on Resilience

Moreover, presented in the model is social support with indicators support from significant other/s and support from friends showed significant relationship with resilience; family support has no significant correlation.

Moreover, resilience components including social competence, personal competency, and structure style showed significant correlation while social resource and family cohesion have not.

Reflected in Table 9 are the direct effects of the variables on resilience according to the best fit model. It can be gleaned that political skills showed the highest total effect of .857 followed by social support with a total effect of .825, and emotional intelligence with .818 on resilience.

Variables	Direct Effect	Indirect Effect	Total Effect
Social Support	.825	-	.825
Emotional Intelligence	-	.818	.818
Political Skills	-	.857	.857

Table 9: Direct and Indirect Effects of the Independent Variables on Resilience of Best Fit Model

With regards to the regression weights measuring the effects between measured and latent variables, the best fit model showed social support with a Beta of .939 on resilience as shown in Table 10.

Moreover, Table 11 reflected the fitness of the model to the criterion set on this study. The P-value, CMIN/DF, GFI, CFI, NFI, TLI, RMSEA, and P-close indices all showed figures that are within the acceptable range. The chi-square divided by the degrees of freedom is 1.548 with the probability of 0.074. Accordingly, the RMSEA index is .036 which is less than 0.05, with its corresponding p-close of .790

			Estimate	S.E.	Beta	C.R.	P-value
Emotional Intelligence	<---	Political Skills	1.049	.057	.972	18.447	***
Social Support	<---	Emotional Intelligence	.991	.078	1.060	12.697	***
Resilience	<---	Social Support	.825	.070	.939	11.841	***
SSO	<---	Social Support	1.000		.552		
SFF	<---	Social Support	.991	.074	.748	13.458	***
EMP	<---	Emotional Intelligence	1.000		.862		
SEA	<---	Emotional Intelligence	.927	.039	.842	23.963	***
APS	<---	Political Skills	1.000		.830		
SOA	<---	Political Skills	1.004	.053	.801	19.108	***
SOC	<---	Resilience	1.000		.743		
PEC	<---	Resilience	1.146	.063	.863	18.047	***
STS	<---	Resilience	1.022	.065	.827	15.722	***

Table 10: Estimates of Variable Regression Weights in Generated Best Fit Model

Legend:

SFF-Support from friends
SSO-Support from significant others
SEA-Self-awareness

EMP-Empathy
SOA-Social astuteness
APS-Apparent sincerity

SOC-Social competence
PEC-Personal Competence
STS-Structured style

which is greater than 0.05. Further, details of other indices such as GFI showed (0.987>0.95), CFI (0.997>0.95), NFI (0.991>0.95, and TLI (0.993>0.95). The figures for each index satisfied the requirement of the goodness of fit measures.

K. Establishing the Best Structural Model

This section presents the analysis on the interrelationships among social support, emotional intelligence, and political skills to the resilience of jail officers in Region XI. There are four alternative models, together with their related tables which are appended, established to achieve the best fit model of resilience of jail officers.

INDEX	CRITERION	MODEL FIT VALUE
P-value	> 0.05	.074
CMIN/DF	$0 < \text{value} < 2$	1.548
GFI	> 0.95	.987
CFI	> 0.95	.997
NFI	> 0.95	.991
TLI	> 0.95	.993
RMSEA	< 0.05	.036
P-Close	> 0.05	.790

Table 11: Goodness of Fit Measures of Structural Best Fit Model

Legend:

CMIN/DF	-	Chi-Square/Degrees of Freedom
NFI	-	Normed Fit Index
TLI	-	Tucker-Lewis Index
CFI	-	Comparative Fit Index
GFI	-	Goodness of Fit Index
RMSEA	-	Root Means Square of Error Approximation
P-close	-	P of Close Fit

The structural model identifies relationships between the latent variables, and the measurement model indicates the measure loads on each factor to their latent constructs.

Additionally, the evaluation of fit was also utilized as a benchmark for accepting or rejecting the model. This is based on the causal connection between the latent variable and the several latent variables. The link between endogenous and exogenous variables is also established. Once a structural model has a good fit, it means that the practical relationships between variables suggested by the model are consistent. The significance and direction of the relationships between these variables are estimated by the model parameters.

Reflected in Table 12 is the summary of goodness of fit measures of the five generated models. Evidently, this comparison of figures displayed the difference of each generated model and the best fit model that is within the acceptable range.

Model	P-value (>0.05)	CMIN / DF (0<value<2)	GFI (>0.95)	CFI (>0.95)	NFI (>0.95)	TLI (>0.95)	RMSEA (<0.05)	P-close (>0.05)
1	.000	20.037	.640	.704	.694	.653	.211	.000
2	.000	14.936	.692	.787	.776	.746	.181	.000
3	.000	12.769	.682	.819	.807	.785	.166	.000
4	.000	12.765	.684	.822	.810	.786	.166	.000
5	.074	1.548	.987	.997	.991	.993	.036	.790

Table 12: Summary of Goodness of Fit Measures of the Five Generated Models

Legend:CMIN/DF – *Chi Square/Degrees of Freedom*NFI – *Normed Fit Index*GFI – *Goodness of Fit Index*TLI – *Tucker-Lewis Index*RMSEA – *Root Mean Square of Error Approximation*CFI – *Comparative Fit Index*

The goodness of fit measures included the p-value that is greater or equal to 0.05, the Chi-square/degrees of freedom value should be less than 5 with its corresponding. The Goodness of Fit, Comparative Fit Index, Normed Fit Index, Tucker-Lewis Index must be all greater than 0.95. The Root Mean Square of Error Approximation value must be less than 0.05 and its corresponding p-close value must be greater to 0.05.

As seen in the appended Table 7, the first to fourth generated models showed the causal relationship of exogenous variables namely social support, emotional intelligence, and political skills to the endogenous variable resilience. These models showed a poor fit considering that calculated numbers are outside the acceptable range of values. Model 1 failed to meet all the criteria set. In Model 2 in the table shows that indices GFI, CFI, NFI, and TLI were 0.692, 0.787, 0.776, and 0.746, respectively emphasizing a non-fit value to their respective criterion. Moreover, results for Model 3 shows that there is none among the value that meets to the criteria. Furthermore, the data for Model 5 revealed that P-value, CMIN/DF, GFI, CFI, NFI, TLI, RMSEA and P-close did not meet the standards of the criterion with .000, 12.765, .684, .822, .810, .786, .166 and .000 respectively. On the contrary, the fifth model illustrated the causal relationship of exogenous variables political skills represented by measured variables social astuteness and apparent sincerity to exogenous variable emotional intelligence while emotional intelligence represented by measured variables self-awareness and empathy to exogenous variable social support represented by measured variables support from significant other/s and support from friends to the endogenous variable resilience represented by measured variables social competence, personal competency and structured style.

In fact, data showed that the modified model presented a causal link of exogenous variable social support to the endogenous variable resilience. From this result, it can be gleaned that the null hypothesis presented in the beginning of this study is rejected. Indeed, there is a causal model that best fit on the resilience of jail officers in Region XI. As described, the model would show that there is really correlation among political skills, emotional intelligence, social support, and professionalism. Findings showed that political skills positively influence emotional intelligence, then emotional intelligence significantly influence social support, and social support notably influence resilience.

CHAPTER 4

DISCUSSION

This chapter introduces the discussion of the statistically supported conclusions on the social support, emotional intelligence, political skills, and resilience of jail officers in the Davao Region. Discussions of the importance of the connection between and influence of the independent variables on resilience, as well as the construct of the best fit model on resilience, are comprehensively presented with supporting tenets, concepts, ideas, and theories that aided in securing the finding and recommendation of the study.

A. Social Support of Jail Officers

The very high level of social support in terms of family support of jail officers is related to the perspective of Song, Son, and Lin (2011) which stated that parents of jail officers who constantly and unwaiveringly gave on going motivation, financial support, and conditional love help them carry out their mission better. Similarly, Armstrong, Atkin-Plunk, and Wells (2015) strengthened the findings which stated that hispanic jail officers were pleased with their jobs because their families were supporting them making them more happy with their work and feel no burden on their problems and disputes despite the peculiarities of being in direct contact with an incarcerated population in confined space which bring obstacles to maintaining work-family balance that affects the well-being of officers. In addition, findings is also analogous to Nickerson and Nagle (2004) that the family is the first and most important source of support, which is also linked to higher levels of life satisfaction; Rueger, Malecki, and Demaray (2010) which stated that family support lowers depression; and Kerr, et al (2006) which stated that family support can lessen hopelessness.

On the other hand, the high level of support from jail officers' friends is consistent with the findings of Cobbina (2010), who discovered that officers view friends and supervisory officers as one of the critical members of their positive support networks, providing emotional support, motivation, and concrete assistance, such as information or assistance in meeting their needs. The high result of support from friends is congruent to the concept of Song, Son, and Lin (2011) who claimed that providing support for both men and women is positively related to self-reported wellbeing. It helps when someone listens to people who want to talk about problems or stress and supports and comforts people who experience hardship. Someone's presence to rely on for support motivates them to work effectively. Social support goes deeper that its common purpose as a stress buffer and plays many roles in health and disease social organization. It may directly, or indirectly, protect health by reducing other health risks.

Moreover, the very high level of support from significant other/s of jail officers is along side of Valera, Chang, Hernández, and Cooper (2015) who mentioned that romantic partners provided another significant kin relationship for prison officers on social support. Positive examples included displays of love and the ability to seek support from your friends with problems. Most of the emotional and practical support given to romantic relationships was reciprocated. Such close friends or partners shared parental duties for helpful support, including finances, housing, and childcare, with them.

B. Emotional Intelligence of Jail Officers

The theory put forth by Gibson (2017) that self-awareness is the ability to recognize and understand one's own emotions as well as how those feelings affect others is brought to light by the high level of self-awareness among jail officers. Individuals that have emotional intelligence also use this understanding to regulate their behavior and interactions with others. Prison employees are those who are paid to work in prisons and undertake a variety of tasks, such as responsibilities in the institution's health and protection (officers and security staff rankings), which includes educating them about their practices and how it affects their jobs and coworkers.

Additionally, this result is in line with the theory put forth by Muniz & Azam (2017), according to which self-awareness is the capacity to understand one's own emotions accurately and become aware of them as they arise. It serves as a reflection of how a person behaves when responding to others and events. In spite of one's own feelings, it enables one to comprehend and assess the emotions of others. Additionally, this finding backs up Gardner's (2015) theory that police have high emotional intelligence, meaning they have the capacity to monitor their own emotions and those of others, control some emotions by tempering unpleasant sentiments, and enhance positive ones. In other words, emotional control refers to the process by which an individual creates and sustains the positive affective states that have been associated with supporting behavior at work.

Consistently, the high level of self-control demonstrated by jail officers consistently supports the theory put forth by Muniz and Azam (2017), who defined emotional intelligence as the capacity to keep track of one's own and other people's emotions, recognize and label various emotions, and use emotional knowledge to guide behavior. The ability to harness one's emotional sensitivity to stay resilient and positively influence one's actions is known as self-management. A person can effectively control their emotional responses to situations and people through this approach. This is in line with the finding made by Ali, Magadley, and Garner (2011) that uniformed officers must have self-control to carry out their jobs efficiently. Being able to control one's emotions as well as those of others is crucial for uniformed personnel, especially in conflict situations because officers are generally the first to respond to situations involving emotionally distressed persons, usually in times of crisis. The high level of self-control displayed by jail officers was supported by Whitman's (2012) claim that emotionally intelligent people should be able to manage their own emotions, including taming distress, successfully navigating adverse effects, and purposefully removing harmful emotions and thereby preventing the negative effects of these effects from being affected cognitively or behaviorally.

In addition, Cherry (2022) claimed that intrinsic motivation is another important aspect of emotional intelligence, and jail officials' extremely high degree of motivation is comparable to that idea. Motivators other than money, fame, or recognition are important to emotionally intelligent people. They are driven instead by a desire to meet the specific requirements and objectives that are personal to them. They are drawn to high points in an activity, rewards from inside, and flow from entire immersion in it. Action-oriented folks are frequently those who are proficient in this subject. They set goals, are driven to succeed, and look for methods to do better all the time. Additionally, they can be in charge and have a strong sense of dedication.

On the other hand, the high level of empathy displayed by jail staff relates to the idea put forth by Kulkarni, Janakiram, and Kumar (2019), who claimed that people with high levels of emotional intelligence are better able to resolve conflicts through their ability to perceive, take into account, and evaluate emotions. They can also use emotional awareness to control their own emotions as well as those of others, which can help to facilitate decisions that better meet the needs of the parties involved. Clearly, the high level of empathy of jail officers in this study is also connected to the notion of Ali, Magadley, and Garner (2011) which specified that empathy develops good relationships with the group and uses social communication skills and interpersonal relationship skills to deal with other people. The ability to identify emotion in others' facial and postural expressions, for instance, is a component of emotional intelligence. Another example is the appraisal and display of emotion. The ability to discriminate between appropriate and inappropriate emotional expressions, as well as between honesty and dishonesty, is another aspect of this concept. It is crucial for effective communication that both parties can accurately determine the other's emotional state via non-verbal cues. In order to encourage and deepen emotional ties and to promote a deeper understanding of others, expressing one's emotions is an essential component of interpersonal relationships.

The findings of Muniz and Azam (2017), which stated that relationship management is the ability to employ abilities of self-awareness and social awareness effectively when communicating with other people and situations, are further supported by the high degree of relationship management of jail officers. It makes it possible for someone to negotiate conflicts and speak clearly in challenging situations. The idea put forth by Daus and Ashkanasy (2015) also supports the idea that relationship management is a talent that expands emotional awareness and focuses on identifying emotions, recognizing how they are related to one another, and understanding how they may be used to inspire and grow others. Similar insights on emotional intelligence aid in understanding the viewpoint of the employees and effectively lead them in comprehending.

C. Political Skills of Jail Officers

The strong networking skills of jail staff bring to light Dixon's (2015) assertion that Northern Irish prison staff used "political skills," such as deceit and manipulation, to reach a "honorable" agreement, make contact with influential people, and maintain contact with them in order to avoid power and enemies. They can create several networks of alliances both inside and outside the company. The assertion stated by Braddy and Campbell (2014) that people with high networking skills are proficient at creating connections and forming relationships with a variety of social groupings lends more credence to this conclusion. They usually have relationships to significant company stakeholders who have access to limited but essential resources. Employees with great networking skills thrive at getting things done at work efficiently and securing the resources they and their teams need. The idea put forth by Treadway, et al. (2017) argued that people with good networking skills ensure they are ideally positioned to create and take advantage of chances. Additionally, people with excellent networking skills make sure they are strategically positioned to develop and capitalize on opportunities, which supported the high degree of networking skill among correctional officers.

The results of Treadway, et al (2017), who claimed that politically qualified people have a certain style that is unassuming and persuasive and exerts a tremendous impact on others around them, further support the high level of interpersonal influence of correctional officers. Individuals can adjust and calibrate their activities to different contexts using interpersonal impact to elicit the desired responses from other people. The assertion made by Braddy and Campbell (2014) that someone with interpersonal influence skills also employs their vivacious or engaging interpersonal style to persuade others supports the aforementioned findings. They are frequently successful in their attempts to exert control over others because they can make people feel comfortable, build relationships, win people over, and interact well with people. Questioning and listening are crucial interpersonal skills to add into your interpersonal style because coworkers might want to feel heard and understood. It has been shown that affability and friendliness are some of their least valued traits and that displaying warmth and showing interest in others are effective strategies to develop relationship capital, which can then be used to advance present and potential difficulties.

In addition, the high level of social intelligence displayed by jail staff supported the idea put forth by Price, Theis, and Keikbusch (2017) that jail staff should maintain their sense of reason, patience, and understanding. Being in control is frequently necessary while treating prisoners with consideration, empathy, and decency in tense circumstances. This finding supports the idea put forth by Braddy and Campbell (2014) that socially aware people are excellent observers of other people in social settings. They are extremely aware of their own feelings and activities as well as the thoughts, emotions, and behaviors of others. Socially conscious professionals often have a solid feel of what to say and how to act to influence their coworkers since they can understand others in social contexts. They are also adept at making people feel good about themselves. While trying to persuade or influence others, demonstrate to them how the suggested concept helps them achieve their own objectives or interests.

Additionally, Price, et al. (2017) stated that the most important factors that can potentially be managed by a managing prison officer include sincere interest contact, realistic promotion opportunities, the best use of resources, and interpersonal skills. This finding is in line with the very high level of apparent sincerity of jail officers. Moreover, Braddy and Campbell (2014) endorsed the findings that real employees act in a way that other people see as honest, open, and genuine. I also genuinely care about other people. These employees are typically regarded and in a stronger position to influence others through several strategies, such as interpersonal control, because they are not seen as being dishonest or having ulterior objectives. To effectively guide others, one must establish trusted relationships. Honesty must be shown since confidence is developed over time and through several interactions.

D. Resilience of Jail Officers

The high level of resilience in terms of social competency of jail officers is in consonance to the declaration of Matczak and Martowska (2013) who emphasized that social competence that seems especially important in the evolving world that can be implemented in various professional work projects and that which strengthens adolescent resilience and resourcefulness. This form of skill accounts for social competence. Social skills often denoted as socio-psychological skills or soft skills. A good example of this can be the ability to build a relationship and exert control or team management. Therefore, social skills can be described as complex skills that condition an individual's effectiveness in dealing with social circumstances. Likewise, Bańka and Trzeciak (2017) highlighted that these social skills represent both workers and organizations. On the one hand, productive client relationships, successful collaboration with partners in the work cycle, exerting control on others as well as being insusceptible improve productivity in the workplace. This helps individuals to cultivate social activity that is an opportunity to strengthen core competencies and attitudes towards employment, the value of which leads to creating tomorrow's career. Good communication, knowledge of foreign languages, transparency, and continuous growth, dedication, and willingness to work as a team improve the employees' social skills.

In addition, the very high level of social resource is allied to the contention of Cicchetti (2010) who stressed that Culture, society, family, and person are the social tools that are forces of security and vulnerability at multiple influences levels. There is strong evidence that nurturing early caregivers during infancy and childhood may boost resilience and lessen the impacts of supposedly harmful surroundings. Those supportive periods can occur when interventions work best. Correspondingly, Seena and Sundaram (2018) asserted that a mixture of factors allows for resilience. Several studies indicate that loving and supportive relationships within and outside the family are the key factors in resiliency. Relationships building love and confidence, providing role models, and giving support and reassurance help improve the resilience of an employee.

Besides, the very high level of family cohesion of jail officers affirmed the impressions of Cox and Furst (2019) who averred that family stability is one of the protective factors associated with employee involvement and maintaining interaction between a mother and her children will improve family stability and help to serve as a preventive measure against stress and problems. Similarly, Askeland et al (2019) who avowed that resilience in working adults is likely to become increasingly important factors relating to near relatives, as this provides not only financial support but also moral support to make a better decision for oneself.

Moreover, the very high level of personal competency of jail officers is in consonance to the notion of Kowalczyk (2014) which claimed that competence perceived as a characteristic derives from the approach to individual differences. Competence is attributed to an individual's talents and abilities, as well as the overall experience and behaviors they use in a successful practice. Likewise, Silvester, Wyatt and Randal (2014) maintained that resilience encompasses the learning factor, early sensitizing experiences, and features of personality, how individuals judge their situations, and the effect of defense mechanisms. Having a robust influence on how well a person takes his or her decisions.

Furthermore, the high level of resilience in terms of structure style of jail officers is confirmed by the notion of Seena and Sundaram (2018) who stated that resilience is correlated with many aspects, like the willingness to make practical decisions and to take action to execute them. The desire to obey the rules to accomplish the goals despite tough times with a constructive perception of oneself and faith in one's skills and power. In a similar vein, Folke (2016) claimed that the emphasis is on resilience as persistence, adaptability, and transformability of complex social-ecological adaptive systems, thereby elaborating on the concept's dynamic and forward-looking aspect. Resilience then further defines the trait of controlling human actions to predict and overcome risks to their life and primary objectives. It encompasses some of the critical components, with a focus on versatility, dealing with unpredictable and unplanned circumstances and reacting immediately to incidents, with exceptional coordination and resource management to participate at crucial moments.

E. Correlations Between Variables

The null hypothesis was rejected in favor of the alternative theory, according to the significance on the relationship between social support and resilience of jail officers. The overall findings on the correlations between social support indicators, such as support from family, friends, and significant others, show a significant relationship with resilience indicators, such as social competence, social resource, family cohesion, personal competence, and structured style. The results corroborate the assertion Cherry (2019) that social support is an additional important factor that fosters resilience. People with good mental faculties typically have family and friends to lean on when circumstances are tough. Riopel (2019) also verified and suggested that there are a variety of approaches to increase resilience, including having a stronger support network, preserving positive connections, improving one's self-image, and adopting a positive outlook.

Additionally, the importance of the association between jail officers' emotional intelligence and resilience suggested that the null hypothesis should be rejected in favor of the alternative conclusion that the two variables are significantly associated. Indications of resilience such as social competence, social resource, family cohesion, personal competence, and structured style significantly correlate with indicators of emotional intelligence in terms of self-awareness, self-management, motivation, empathy, and relationship management. The results back up the claim made by Magnano, Craparo, and Paolillo (2015) that emotional intelligence deals with the self-regulatory mechanisms of feelings and motivation that enable people to make changes to achieve individual, group, and organizational objectives; emotional intelligence is strongly linked to employee performance and individual growth within an organizational setting. Armstrong, Galligan, and Critchley (2011) also added that emotional intelligence may be directly linked to resilience, which makes emotional intelligence adaptive in stressful circumstances.

It follows that there is a significant association between jail officials' political skills and resilience. The significance on the relationship between political skills and resilience shows the rejection of the null hypothesis. This connotes that as political skills increase, there is also a corresponding increase on the resilience of jail officers. The results back up the notion put forth by Silvester, Wyatt, and Randall (2014), who claimed that political skills are necessary for creating networks, convincing people, and reaching consensus. Political acumen has also been proven to predict manager performance levels and career success; thus, political skills are positively associated with resilience ratings, especially on aspects of position involving persuasion and building relationships.

Hence, the propositions cited in the theoretical framework are affirmed by the results of this study. Social support positively influences resilience supports the findings of Riopel (2019) who found out that there are numerous techniques to boost resilience which involve getting a good support system and preserving helpful connections. Resilience is predicted by emotional intelligence, supporting the claim made by Trigueros, Padilla, Aguilar-Parra, Rocamora, Morales-Gázquez, and López-Liria (2020), who found a favorable correlation between emotional intelligence and resilience. Lastly, political skills affect resilience strengthens that the premise of Hochwarter et al (2010) which pointed that a high degree of political ability that a person perceives correlates with a high level of optimistic resilience.

F. Regression Analysis on the Influence of Social Support, Emotional Intelligence and Political Skills to Resilience

The significance of the relationship between the variables and resilience revealed that social support, particularly support from friends and significant other(s), is a predictor of resilience in jail officials. On the other hand, emotional intelligence is a good predictor of resilience specifically on self-awareness and empathy. Moreover, political skills are also a good predictor of resilience predominantly on social astuteness and apparent sincerity. Evidently, the results are consistent with the conceptual analyses of Hamdan-Mansour, Azzeghaiby, Alzoghaibi, Badawi, Nassar, and Shaheen (2014), Gungormus, Okanli, Kocabeyoglu (2015), and Inci, and Temel (2016), which stated that studies have demonstrated a relationship between the degree of resilience experienced and demonstrated and the perception of social support. In the same vein, the study backs up the claim made by Magnano, Craparo, and Paolillo (2016) that emotional intelligence deals with the self-regulatory mechanisms of motivation and feelings that enable people to make changes to achieve individual, group, and organizational objectives; emotional intelligence is strongly linked to employee performance and individual growth in an organizational setting. Hence, the precursor to resilience is emotional intelligence. Certainly, the study's findings supported the idea put forth by Holmberg, Larsson, and Bäckström (2016), which proposed that political skills may be utilized to operationalize and measure specific, contextually relevant consequences of an organization's growth. The political ability has been shown to be an effective regulator of presumed entitlement actions by being immune to oneself.

G. Best Fit Model for Resilience

Five different models were examined to better understand how social support, emotional quotient, and resilience of jail officers interacted. They underwent testing to determine the jail officers' resilience best fit model. The two sub models that can be dissociated from each model's framework are the measurement model and the structural model. While the structural model establishes relationships among the latent variables, the measurement model depicts the measure loads on each factor to their respective latent constructs. Additionally, the evaluation of fit served as a benchmark for approving or rejecting the model. Based on the findings, the model evidently brightens the essentials of social support, emotional intelligence, and political skills as predictors of resilience. Social support, emotional intelligence, and political skills are important components of jail officers to appropriately manage their ability to cope up challenges in life in performing their mission and goals in jail facility. Hence, the findings highlighted that resilience of jail officers to succeed must be anchored on social support particularly support from friends and support from significant other/s. Likewise, critical consideration on the inclusion of emotional intelligence is necessary to meet the guarantee of resilience: self-awareness and empathy. Moreover, significant attention of the presence of political skills is essential also to meet resilience specifically social astuteness and apparent sincerity.

The model 5 that was generated supports the assertion Cherry (2019) that social support is yet another important factor that boosts resilience. People with good mental faculties typically have family and friends to lean on when circumstances are tough. The best fit model of resilience appears to corroborate Magnano, Craparo, and Paolillo's (2015) assertion that emotional intelligence addresses self-regulatory processes of feelings and motivation that enable people to make changes to achieve person, group, and organizational objectives; emotional intelligence is heavily associated with individual development and achievement in an organizational environment and with employee performance. Hence, the precursor to resilience is emotional intelligence. Political skills are positively associated with resilience ratings, particularly on aspects of position involving persuasion and relationship building, which is evidently supported by the fifth model of resilience. According to Silvester, Wyatt, and Randall (2014), political skills are essential for building networks, persuading others, and achieving consensus and have been shown to predict performance levels for managers and career success.

H. Conclusion

Conclusive statements were drawn based on the findings of the study, the level of social support is very high except for the support from friends' indicator with high level. The level of emotional intelligence is high excluding motivation indicator with very high level. The level of political skills is high while the level of resilience is very high.

On the other hand, there are significant relationships between social support and resilience, emotional intelligence and resilience, and political skills and resilience. Moreover, social support, emotional intelligence, and political skills are predictors of jail officers. Furthermore, generated model 5 fits resilience. This means that the causes of resilience lean on the social support, emotional intelligence, and political skills which is stimulated by prison managers and correctional advocates. In addition, resilience is best anchored on social support, emotional intelligence, and political skills signifying that the extent of social support, emotional intelligence, and political skills mean higher resilience of jail officers.

I. Recommendation

The results and findings state that social support, emotional intelligence, and political skills are predictors of resilience. To empower jail officers through unique capacity building programs and initiatives, top management officials may decide to reform their support system, emotional reinforcement, and policies. Greater focus must be placed on methods that may inform and empower all correctional staff members about their performance. The results, on the other hand, may be used as benchmark data by jail wardens and superintendents to revise policies, plans, and programs that will support maintaining a greater degree of resilience in jail officers. Future researchers who wish to use the adopted questionnaire in the present study may consider validating the instrument using exploratory factor analysis (EFA) or confirmatory factor analysis (CFA). In addition, future researchers may consider other predictor variables of resilience and shall conduct similar study across jail or prison facilities particularly in Region XI.

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